

**Addressing Achievement Gaps between Disadvantaged and non-
Disadvantaged Students at Primary and Post-primary Level:
A Review of Recent International Research**

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Summary

- While the performance of low-SES (socioeconomically disadvantaged) students has improved over time internationally and in Ireland (e.g., OECD, 2020; Hanushek et al., 2020; Kavanagh et al., 2017), these and other studies (e.g., Bai et al., 2001; Cheung et al., 2021) show that gaps in performance between high- and low-SES students persist at primary and post-primary levels and are difficult to bridge. Hence, interventions or strategies that improve overall performance at system level, including the performance of both high- and low-achievers, may not succeed in bridging achievement gaps.
- Nevertheless, there is evidence that individual school-based and out-of-school interventions can accelerate the performance of low-SES students. Programmes in language, literacy and mathematics have all had some effects on student performance (e.g. Marulis & Newman, 2013; Dietrichson et al., 2017, 2020, 2021; Silverman et al., 2020), though outcome measures sometimes focus on short-term gains rather than long-term transfer.
- Features of school-based programmes that are moderately effective in improving the performance of low-SES students at primary and post-primary levels include peer-assisted learning, small-group instruction (up to 5 children) and progress monitoring (Dietrichson et al., 2017, 2020, 2021). Other features, with smaller, but still significant effect sizes, include computer-assisted instruction, coaching of teachers and medium group size (more than 5 children, but fewer than a whole class).
- In considering the effectiveness of programmes for low-SES/disadvantaged students, it is useful to make a distinction between those that are school-based (in that they are implemented in a school in particular classes or grade levels), and those that are school-wide or whole-school. The research evidence shows that school-wide programs such as Success for All (Slavin et al., 1993, cited in Cheung et al., 2021) also produce small to moderate effect sizes. Such programmes are typically intensive (two to three years in length) and may involve re-grouping children by ability across class levels. They may also include one-to-one or paired tutoring in the early grades if progress within a group is not adequate (Cheung et al., 2021). In order to reduce variation in implementation, they may include scripted lessons. A limitation of school-wide programmes is that they often focus on children in kindergarten to second grade, with less emphasis on

unconstrained skills such as vocabulary and comprehension, and more on constrained skills such as phonological skills and word reading. Furthermore, the impact of cross-age and grade level regrouping on children's reading motivation, engagement and sense of self-efficacy have not been measured or reported as an outcome in studies included in meta-analyses (e.g., Cheung et al., 2021).

- While early intervention programmes can be effective (Fantuzzo, 2011; Cheung et al. 2021; Dockrell et al., 2021), they need to be followed up with appropriate longer-term supports, extending into the senior primary classes and post-primary level as the demands and complexities of texts, including their structure and vocabulary, continue to rise (Swanson et al., 2017; Dietrichson et al. 2017, 2020; Cheung et al., 2021).
- There is evidence to suggest that multi-tiered systems are effective in addressing literacy underachievement (Swanson et al., 2017). In such systems, a high-priority is put on optimising the quality of classroom instruction to benefit all children and to minimise the numbers of children requiring Tier 2 (small group tutoring) or Tier 3 (one-to-one tutoring)
- Puzio et al. (2020) make the point that, while differentiated instruction using small groups is an evidence-based practice, it does not represent a 'silver bullet', as there can be considerable variation in how teachers differentiate instruction within groups. This has implications for the type of support provided to teachers to operate effectively within groups and make appropriate decisions in differentiating instruction and grouping children.
- Although executive functioning (defined as working memory, attention shifting and inhibition) has been shown to correlate only modestly with socioeconomic status after controlling for intelligence, Lawson et al. (2018) note that it is a risk factor for low-SES students, and that small differences in early childhood may have cumulative consequences across domains of development, including later academic performance (a phenomenon termed 'developmental cascades').
- Spatial knowledge or spatial reasoning has been identified as a skill that can be leveraged against the weak foundations in mathematics of some low-SES students (Singh, 2015).
- Research has established links between literacy performance and summer vacation reading loss (Davies & Aurini, 2013; Allington & McGill Franzen, 2020), reading volume (Lindsay, 2018; Torppa et al., 2020; Van Bergen et al., 2020, cited in Allington

& McGill Franzen, 2020), print exposure and leisure reading (Mol & Bus, 2011) and access to books and libraries (Neuman & Celano, 2001; Neuman & Moland, 2019, cited in Allington & McGill Franzen, 2020); all of these are most problematic and challenging for children in low-SES communities who do not have the same access to such resources as their more affluent peers.

- Several studies (Cooper, 1996, cited in Weir et al. 2017; Davies & Aurini, 2013) have found that the summer loss for children from low-SES communities is roughly equivalent to the loss of a month of instruction while children from high-SES communities gain a month. Additionally, Davies and Aurini (2013), in a well-designed study, reported that in June children in the lowest-SES quartile in the study were already 5.28 months behind those in the highest SES-quartile and with summer loss they began the next school year over 7 months behind. Weir et al. (2017), citing Alexander et al. (2007), found disadvantaged children to be the equivalent of nearly three grade levels behind their more advantaged peers by 5th grade. Summer reading loss appears to be significant and cumulative over schooling.
- There are some differences in the literature on the intensity that is required in summer reading programmes to effect significant change in performance, with some evidence showing that programmes involving choice of materials by students (i.e., six books), but within minimal adult intervention (Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2021), can be effective. Kim & Quinn (2013, cited in Weir et al., 2017) found the largest effect sizes were associated with the most resource-intensive classroom-based interventions (i.e. those with 13 children or fewer, those with 4 to 8 hours daily instructional time, and those with 70 to 175 hours total programme time). Dietrichson et al. (2017) reported very small effect sizes. Interventions reviewed supplied books to students to read and work with during the summer with librarians or reading coaches playing a role in book selection and required activities.
- Age 8-9 (grade 2-3) is a critical time in literacy and mathematics development, as achievement at this juncture predicts later achievement (Torppa et al., 2020 cited in Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2021; Singh et al., 2015). The language and reading abilities of frequent readers differ from those who read less often (Mol & Bus, 2011), contributing to ‘Matthew Effects’ in reading (Stanovich, 1986). Children who read less (including many low-SES children) also tend to have reduced vocabulary size, weaker comprehension and less conceptual knowledge, all of which are related to achievement.

Mol and Bus found moderate to strong correlations between print exposure, oral language and reading outcomes regardless of age, leading them to conclude that *'the outcomes support an upward spiral of causality'* (p.267) as the impact of print exposure increased with each year of education.

- Studies demonstrate that for lower-achievers, correlations between print exposure and reading skills are even stronger than for high-ability readers and that they out-perform their lower-ability peers who don't have access to or engage in leisure reading (Mol & Bus, 2011).
- Children who read for pleasure during school in addition to reading during instruction time have higher achievement than those that do not (Lewis & Samuels, 2005, cited in Allington & McGill Franzen, 2021). Lewis and Samuels's (2005) meta- analysis of 49 studies which examined the effects of providing students time to read independently during school. They reported moderately strong effect sizes from experimental studies which *'provided clear causal evidence that students who have in- school independent reading time in addition to regular reading instruction, do significantly better on measures of reading achievement than peers who have not'* (p. 2). Such a finding is linked to reading volume, reading engagement and Matthew effects in reading achievement and could be a way to increase reading opportunities for children from low SES backgrounds who do not have access to a wide range of books in the home.
- Aspects of early reading and mathematical development have been found to influence one another. Singh et al. (2015) cited a number of studies that linked improvement in phonological skills (an aspect of reading development) to improvement in aspects of mathematics. Hecht et al. (2001) showed that phonological processing (phonological memory, rate of access to phonological codes in long-term memory, and phonological awareness) increased early mathematics achievement and was related to mathematics computation skills.
- The expectations of both parents and teachers play an important role in children's performance, with some teachers holding lower expectations for lower-SES students (Wang et al., 2018). Class-level expectations have been shown to be more significant for student learning than individual student expectations (Rubie, 2007). Factors that can mediate teacher expectations include students' self-concept, their self-efficacy and their

self-expectations. Moreover, in the case of low-SES students, more positive parent expectations can override low teacher expectations (Benner & Mistry, 2007).

Recommendations

Pillar 1: Enabling Parents and Communities

- Parents should be made aware of the importance of their expectations as mediators of student learning, with positive expectations likely to have a positive impact on performance.

Pillar 2: Teachers and ECEC CPD (Teacher Education)

- In order for differentiation to be an effective component of intervention programmes in literacy and numeracy, teachers should be supported in using formative assessment in their planning and teaching to optimise impact (Puzio et al., 2020).
- Professional development for teachers should include attention to research-based instructional strategies for key literacy skills (phonemic awareness, phonics, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension, writing, spelling, oral language). In addition, it should include attention to the research on reading volume and reading for pleasure and consideration should be given to how to optimise volume of reading and engagement both in and out of school (Allington & McGill Franzen, 2021)
- Teachers should become aware of the impact of their expectations on the performance of low-SES students, and communicate appropriately-high expectations to all students (Wang et al., 2018). Teachers should note the importance of student self-concept, their self-efficacy and their self-expectations in mediating teacher expectations (Rubie, 2007).

Pillar 3: School and ECEC leadership

- Principals and leadership teams in schools should be provided with professional development in how to lead whole school change in line with research-based strategies in literacy, and monitor the impact of changes in children's literacy development so instruction can be adapted as required (Cheung et al., 2021).

Pillar 4: Curriculum and the learning experience

- Effective school-based interventions for primary and post-primary students who are at risk of low achievement in literacy and numeracy should include peer-assisted instruction (same age peer-tutoring or cooperative learning in pairs), small-group teaching (groups of five children or less), and progress monitoring and feedback (Dietrichson, 2017, 2020, 2021). Children should receive small group literacy tutoring in addition to classroom instruction (Cheung et al., 2021). However, effectiveness is contingent on teacher knowledge and expertise in assessment and differentiation of practices according to student needs (Puzio et al., 2020).
- For school-wide or whole-school interventions in literacy to be effective, they should be intensive (with, for example, a 90-minute daily block), use research-based instructional strategies involving decoding/spelling, vocabulary development, fluency, comprehension and writing, and provide additional tutoring for students who are not making adequate progress (Cheung et al., 2021).
- The early years of schooling (up to 8 years) are a critical period for skills development in literacy (Torpaa et al., 2020, cited in Allington and McGill-Franzen, 2021) and numeracy (Singh et al., 2015). Hence, every effort should be made to ensure that disadvantaged children are strongly supported to develop key language, literacy and mathematical skills in the Junior primary classes. In addition, intervention programmes, whether school-based or school-wide, should continue beyond the period of initial reading instruction (Infants to Second Class), in recognition of the increased literacy and numeracy challenges experienced by disadvantaged pupils beyond that period (e.g., Swanson et al., 2017; Cheung et al. 2021).
- The learning of disadvantaged students should be supported by integrating the development of executive functioning, metacognitive strategies and spatial reasoning into teaching and learning experiences (Lawson, 2018; Singh, 2015).
- Given the overall effectiveness of intervention programmes in mathematics for disadvantaged students at primary and post-primary levels (e.g., Dietrichson et al., 2017, 2020), the implementation of such programmes should be expanded.

Pillar 5: Students with additional learning needs

- Socio-economically disadvantaged children who also have developmental disorders are particularly at risk of very low achievement in literacy and numeracy (Taylor et al.,

2019; these children should be given priority in the allocation of instructional resources in schools.

- Given the research on summer loss (Weir et al, 2017; Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2021; Davies & Aurini), careful attention should be given to the design and implementation of summer reading interventions which should include research-based instructional strategies in key literacy skills, attention to reading engagement, and supplying children with self-selected books for summer reading.
- Given that leisure time reading, access to books and high-quality libraries in schools, classrooms and communities have been linked to reading engagement and achievement (Pribesh, Gavigan & Dickinson, 2011; Neumann & Celano, 2001; Neumann & Moland, 2019 cited in Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2021; Mol & Bus, 2011), teachers should be provided with advice on how to stay up to date with children’s literature in a range of genres, how to select literature for the classroom and specific funding provided for this purpose. High-quality libraries should be provided in highly disadvantaged communities and every effort should be made to optimise home-school-community links between libraries, schools and families.

Pillar 6: Assessment and evaluation to support learning in literacy and numeracy

- While the performance of low-SES students has improved on some national assessments in literacy and numeracy in recent years, gaps between low-SES and high-SES students persist in Ireland and elsewhere (Weir et al.,2017; Bai et al., 2021). Hence, schools and teachers working with disadvantaged children should be supported in monitoring the effects of interventions in literacy and numeracy more closely across a range of indicators to ensure that progress is accelerated and sustained.
- In line with the importance attributed to differentiation in effective intervention programmes in literacy and numeracy (Puzio et al., 2020), teachers working with disadvantaged pupils should be supported in the effective use of formative assessment in intervention programmes. Attention should be given to frequency of assessment, interpretation of assessment data and how to use it to select appropriate instructional strategies.

Introduction

This paper looks at research on addressing achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy arising from differences in socioeconomic status among students and schools. The paper is intended to complement a paper in the same series by French (2022), which looks at disadvantaged and early childhood education and care. Readers are also referred to a report by Shiel and Kennedy (2022) which outlines research findings on disadvantage in Ireland.

Parts of the current paper draw on systemic reviews and meta-analyses. Where systematic reviews and meta-analyses are not available, we draw on research studies and more traditional research reviews (e.g., Weir et al., 2017).

The key questions underpinning this report are as follows:

- Have achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy increased or reduced internationally in recent years?
- What do systematic reviews and meta-analyses say about the effectiveness of interventions designed to address achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy associated with low-SES?
- What research is available on the extent of summer learning loss among low-SES students and strategies to address learning loss, where it occurs?
- How is low-SES related to the expectations of teachers working with low-SES students, and what factors mediate those expectations?

The chapter is divided into ten sections. The first describes the methodology underpinning the search of databases for suitable studies. The second looks at achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy, including factors associated with those gaps. The third looks at gaps in exposure to reading, associations between reading volume and reading achievement, and summer learning loss. The fourth section considers changes in achievement gaps over time, with attention to factors needed to address such gaps effectively. The fifth section looks at the effects of general interventions designed to reduce achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy at both primary and post-primary levels, while the sixth looks at interventions focused on universal provision in multi-tiered systems. The seventh section looks at school-wide interventions designed to address learning gaps in schools serving low-SES students. The eighth section looks at interventions involving executive functioning and the ninth looks at digital literacies and disadvantage. The final section considers teacher expectations and socio-economic status.

Methodology

A description of the methodology underpinning this report is given in Appendix A, including the search strategy employed. A summary of each of the studies contributing to the report is given in Appendix B.

Achievement Gaps in Literacy and Numeracy

A key focus of research on socio-economic disadvantage has been the identification of gaps in achievement, and efforts to close those gaps. Gaps in achievement appear early and seem to persist. Hart and Risley (2003) estimated a gap of 30 million words between the accumulated experience with words that the average child from a professional family is likely to be exposed to by age 3, compared with the average child from a poor family (though see, for example, Dyson's (2015) critique of that work). Research by Oxford Primary (2018) cites the belief expressed by a majority of primary and post-primary teachers in a survey they conducted in the UK that the word gap (the difference in vocabulary knowledge between high- and low-SES children) is increasing (worsening) over time, and that the gap manifests itself through difficulty in working independently, poorer examination results, and slower than expected progress in English and other subjects. Achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy linked to socio-economic status have been reported in the national (e.g., Gillece et al., 2020) and international literature (e.g., OECD, 2018; Hanushek et al., 2020).

Factors Associated with Achievement Gaps

A key factor associated with performance on multiple aspects of literacy (and well-being more broadly) is socioeconomic status (SES). On average, students in schools with large numbers of disadvantaged students typically perform less well on assessments of literacy than their counterparts in schools with large proportions of more advantaged students (e.g., Eivers, Shiel & Short, 2005; DfE, 2021). Socioeconomic disadvantage can also impact on performance at the individual student level, with low-SES students at greater risk of low achievement in literacy than their more advantaged peers. The OECD (2018) uses the term 'double disadvantage' to describe the situation of disadvantaged students attending disadvantaged schools or schools with large numbers of other disadvantaged students.

According to the American Psychological Association (APA, n.d.), SES encompasses not just income (of students' parents), but also educational attainment, financial security, subjective perceptions of social status and social class. They note that a key characteristic of low-SES is its persistence, from birth through formal schooling and into adulthood. APA and others (e.g., Hart & Risley, 2003; OECD, 2018; Oxford Primary, 2018) have noted a number of literacy-related factors associated with low-SES which can contribute, either individually or in combination, to gaps in literacy achievement, including: home experiences that may be less conducive to developing fundamental skills for reading acquisition such as phonological awareness, vocabulary and oral discourse; more limited access to materials and experiences at home, including books, computers, toys and games; more limited access to appropriate educational opportunities, with school systems in less-affluent areas often under-resourced; and lack of access to more experienced teachers.

A concept that is related to socioeconomic disadvantage is equity in education. The OECD (2018) defines this as the provision of equal learning opportunities to all students so that students of different socioeconomic status (or gender, or immigrant background) achieve similar levels of academic performance in key cognitive domains such as reading literacy, and similar levels of social and emotional wellbeing (defined as life satisfaction, self-confidence and social integration). The organisation clarifies that equity 'does not mean that all students obtain equal education outcomes, but rather that differences in student outcomes are unrelated to their background or to economic and social circumstances over which students have no control' (p. 13).

Evidence from the UK indicates that, at school entry, up to 40% of children in low-SES contexts have delayed language (Law, McBean & Rush., 2011). Law et al. (2013) note that, when studies of whole populations are examined, a clear 'social gradient' for language can be observed, with children from the most disadvantaged backgrounds on average having lower language skills than those in the least disadvantaged groups. The same study noted that both environmental and genetic factors play a role in language delay, with the child's environment playing a more critical role in the early years and the most disadvantaged children least likely to 'catch up'.

While Aikens and Barbarin (2008) showed that family characteristics (defined as home literacy environment, parental involvement in school, and parental role strain) made the largest contribution to the prediction of initial kindergarten reading differences, they also reported that school and neighbourhood conditions (described as poverty concentration and number of students with reading difficulties) impacted more strongly on

reading achievement at higher grade levels. Multi-level models of reading performance at post-primary level (e.g., Shiel et al., 2022) show that a range of factors can operate simultaneously to explain reading achievement, including school- and student-level SES, number of books in the home, students' attitude to reading, students' engagement in reading (frequency of reading for enjoyment), parents' engagement in reading, students' endorsement of cognitive and metacognitive reading strategies, and their perception of their competence in reading. These variables combine to explain variation in reading achievement, with negative effects associated with lower values on most of them.

The OECD (2018) noted that disparities in performance related to socio-economic status are evident during the primary school years, and widen throughout students' lives. On average across 11 OECD countries with comparable data, two-thirds of the achievement gap observed in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) at age 15, and more than half of the achievement gap observed among 25-29 year olds on an assessment of adult literacy and numeracy was already apparent among 10-year olds. An implication of this is a need to reduce underachievement in literacy and other curriculum areas among disadvantaged students at as early a stage as possible.

Singh et al. (2015) analysed key predictors at the student and school levels to identify their long-term impact on mathematics achievement from Grade 3 to Grade 10. Their findings indicate that, of all the individual factors, Grade 3 mathematics achievement was the most crucial predictor for future mathematics achievement. Economic disadvantage at the student and school levels also had a negative impact on achievement, with individual characteristics having approximately four times the predictive power of school-level characteristics.

Although not a meta-analysis, Singh et al.'s study is important for a number of reasons. First, it was multi-year study, enabling an analysis of mathematical performance in the same cohorts over time; this contrasts with cross-sectional studies, which focus on the performance of individual cohorts (e.g., students in Grades 2) at a specific point in time. Second, the study examined an important policy issue – whether it is possible to bridge gaps between disadvantaged and non-disadvantaged students in national testing programmes over time. Third, it looked at the impact of prior performance as well as relevant school- and student-level factors, including socioeconomic status. The finding that individual factors such as student socioeconomic status have a far greater impact on achievement than school-level factors led the authors to question why schools are sanctioned for failing to meet targets, when factors such as disadvantage are largely outside their control. It is argued that, instead,

the focus should be on helping to support schools working with a large percentage of economically disadvantaged or underrepresented students. The key role of prior attainment (in this case, mathematics performance at Grade 3) led to the conclusion that early childhood programmes for children in families with disadvantaged socioeconomic background are crucial. The author also suggested identifying other capabilities such as spatial knowledge that could be leveraged against students' weak foundations in mathematics (also see Sobanski, 2002; Uttal et al., 2013).

Finally, Singh et al. cited a number of studies that linked improvement in phonological skills (an aspect of reading development) to improvement in aspects of mathematics. For example, Hecht et al. (2001) showed that phonological processing (phonological memory, rate of access to phonological codes in long-term memory, and phonological awareness) increased early mathematics achievement and was related to mathematics computation skills, while Gersten et al. (2005) found that students with limited phonological processing skills in the early grades were not be able to apply sophisticated counting strategies and compare the magnitudes of numbers or to identify numbers proficiently when they reached Grade 3.

Gaps in Exposure to Reading

Frequent engagement in reading correlates with educational achievement, level of economic success and employment opportunities in adult life. As the National Endowment for the Arts highlighted 'whether or not people read, and indeed how much and how often they read, affects their lives in crucial ways' (NEA, 2007, p.6) and has implications for the functioning of a

democratic society as those who are less skilled at reading are less likely to 'become active in cultural and civic life, most notably in volunteerism and voting' (p.5).

Methodologically, print exposure studies are largely correlational in nature, rather than experimental or quasi-experimental. For this reason, such studies have not received the same attention as other aspects of literacy learning. Influential reports such as the (US) National Reading Panel report (NICHHD, 2000), which synthesised research on reading in order to provide direction to government and school districts on the evidence base for teaching reading, largely ignored the literature on reading for pleasure as a large volume of these studies did not adhere to the experimental research approach favoured by the Panel (i.e., randomized controlled trials). On the other hand, Allington and McGill-Franzen (2021), in their review

of the literature on reading volume and performance, noted that correlational research is widely used in health and medical fields to inform advice to the public (e.g., on dangers of smoking and obesity) which *'denies the argument that such research is of little value and worse unscientific'* (p.5232).

This section reports on studies that have investigated the impact of leisure reading on the development of both foundational skills or 'constrained skills' (e.g. phonics, spelling, high frequency words) and 'unconstrained' skills (Paris, 2005) such as reading comprehension, oral language and vocabulary. It explores questions such as those highlighted by Mol and Bus (2011):

1. Does reading for pleasure make us better and faster readers, more knowledgeable and even better speakers?
2. How do the language and reading abilities of frequent readers differ from those of non-readers at each stage of development?

Other studies have explored the lack of opportunity to read for pleasure due to insufficient emphasis placed on such reading in schools and classrooms, and also poor access to engaging print materials both in and out of school, which particularly affects children in marginalised communities who also experience the so called 'summer slump' (Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2021; Davies & Aurini, 2013).

The Benefits of Print Exposure Across the Education Continuum

Mol and Bus (2011) synthesised 99 studies that explored the impact of reading for pleasure on the development of early literacy skills (e.g., alphabet knowledge and phonological awareness), technical reading (e.g., word identification, accuracy and spelling) and reading comprehension. The findings reported here mirror those of a previous quantitative meta-analysis (Bus et al., 1995) which included 33 studies between 1951 and 1999. Print exposure can be measured in various ways including through self-report questionnaires whereby participants or guardians (in the case of young children) indicate frequency of exposure to text and through a tick box checklist (e.g., authors and book titles with some distractors/fake items) adjusted to age group. Questionnaires are open to bias as respondents may wish to be seen positively as participating in socially desirable practices, or to error as participants may interpret the same questions differently. As highlighted by Sénéchal et al. (1996), a parent may count the sharing of five books in one sitting before bedtime as five sessions, whereas another parent may report it as only one reading occurrence. Checklists are thought to mitigate measurement issues and provide a quick discreet probe into home literacy environments.

Mol and Bus (2011) grouped studies into three categories: (a) Prek-K; (b) Grades 1-12; and (c) college students. Regardless of age, for all measures in the outcome domains, moderate to strong correlations with print exposure were found. They argue that *'the outcomes support an upward spiral of causality'* (p.267) as the impact of print exposure increased with each year of education (e.g., in preschool and kindergarten, it explained 12% of variance in oral language skills, 13% in primary school, 19% in middle school, 30% in high school and 34% in college and university). They posit *'that an early start of shared book reading sets in motion a causal spiral, in which print exposure stimulates language and reading development, which, in turn, stimulates the quantity of print exposure'* (p.285). Shared book reading in early years supports development of positive attitudes toward reading as well as laying the foundation for rich linguistic development and reading skills, as children interact and respond to significant others who read to and with them. It appears that a reciprocal relationship or causation exists between volume of reading and reading proficiency and achievement which Stanovich (1986) termed the 'Matthew effect'. Children who enjoy reading read many more minutes per day than their peers who don't and the more they read, the more proficient they become not only in the development of basic reading skills but also in oral language, vocabulary and conceptual knowledge. A later study, mirroring Mol and Bus's findings, reported that *'children who read even ten minutes a day outside of school, experience substantially higher rates of vocabulary growth between 2nd -5th grade than children who do little or no reading'* (Anderson & Nagy, 1992, p.11).

In contrast, children who don't enjoy reading and or experience reading difficulties tend to read less than their more-able peers, and so are not exposed to the rich, complex and more sophisticated language and syntactical structures of text genres. The correlations for each outcome for each of the three cohorts considered by Mol and Bus (2011) are summarised in Table 1. As the table indicates, the relationship between print exposure and oral language grows progressively stronger as participants grow older. A similar pattern emerged in relation to basic reading skills and IQ from primary to middle school. Correlations were mostly in the moderate range, though one large effect size was found for oral language and print exposure at college level (0.58), with a marginally weaker correlation between exposure and reading comprehension at this level (0.42)¹. A limitation of the meta-analysis Mol and Bus identify is the dearth of studies that have investigated differences in print exposure and SES. Only three of the 14 matched studies were conducted with low SES families. They highlight that children from low SES backgrounds were rarely studied in the youngest age group, and hypothesise that this may be due to the fact that researchers expect floor effects on print

exposure checklists in families with limited means and/or few literacy activities. This seems a reasonable assumption given the finding highlighted earlier that number of books in the home is one of the moderating variables on reading achievement (Shiel et al., 2022). Shared book reading in early years lays the foundation for later reading development (Dobinson & Dockrell., 2021) and lack of exposure to print likely contributes to the word gap at school entry (Hart & Risley, 2003; Oxford Primary, 2018).

Table 1: Effect size correlations between print exposure and component skills of literacy in PreK-K, Grades 1-12 and College/University students

Grade	Age	Effect sizes correlations between print exposure and outcome skills
PreK-K 29 studies	2-6 years (mean age: 56.95 months, <i>SD</i> = 0.40)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● oral language skills (k = 12, r = .34, p = .001) ● receptive vocabulary (k = 9, r = .33, p = .001) ● expressive vocabulary skills (k = 4, r = .35, p = .001).
Grades 1–12 40 studies	6.2 -17.5 years of age (Mean age: 10.23 yrs. <i>SD</i> = 2.61)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● oral language skills (k = 18, r = .45, p = .001) ● reading comprehension (k = 21, r = .36, p = .001). ● word recognition (k = 24, r = .38, p = .001) ● spelling (k = 9, r = .42, p = .001)
College/University 30 studies	Mean age = 21.00 years, <i>SD</i> = 2.32,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● oral language (k = 18, r = .58, p = .001) ● reading comprehension (k = 11, r = .41, p = .001)

K= no. of studies; R= effect size; p= significance; Source: Mol & Bus (2011)¹ Fisher's z value of .10 (r = .10) can be interpreted as a small effect size, .31 (r = .30) as moderate, and .55 (r = .50) as large (Cohen, 1988).

Frequent leisure reading exposes readers to words in multiple forms and contexts, building up a rich association and network of knowledge about word meanings and word parts. It supports the self-teaching hypothesis (Share, 1995, 1999; Cunningham et al., 2002, cited in Mol & Bus, 2011) which posits that readers can unlock unknown words (in reading and spelling) through application of letter-sound relationships that they have been taught, which in turn supports their development as independent readers and writers.

Mol and Bus conclude that reading for pleasure is especially important for low-ability readers (some of whom would also be expected to have low SES). It is critical that they have access to the right books outside of school (age, interest and appropriate reading level) if they are to gain the much-needed practice in basic reading skills and become more accurate and fluent in reading text. Studies demonstrate that, for this cohort, correlations between print exposure and reading skills are even stronger than for high-ability readers and that they outperform their lower-ability peers who don't have access to or engage in such reading. While

explicit instruction is a critical component of literacy development, the additional print exposure gained through leisure reading also plays a significant role, though it has not received the same attention as the research on instructional practices.

Reading Volume and Reading Achievement

Allington and McGill-Franzen (2021) reviewed studies carried out between 2000 and 2021 which went beyond simple correlations and utilised new methodological approaches not available earlier when many correlational studies were conducted. Brenner and Hebert (2010, cited in Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2021) examined the volume of reading expected in six core reading programmes utilised in the US and concluded that daily volume was less than optimum offering only *'seven to 15 minutes of actual reading activity'* (p.5232). Another study cited (Lewis & Samuels, 2005), a meta-analysis of 49 studies examining the effects of providing students time to independently read during school, reported moderately strong d-index effect sizes from experimental studies which *'provided clear causal evidence that students who have in-school independent reading time in addition to regular reading instruction, do significantly better on measures of reading achievement than peers who have not'* (p. 2). Though no such data are available in Ireland, it is important to consider how much time children actually spend engaged in the act of continuous reading during school time. However, time spent reading outside of school has frequently been found to be related to reading achievement (e.g. Kavanagh et al., 2015).

Researchers in Finland (Torppa et al., 2020; Van Bergen et al., 2020 cited in Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2021) have investigated if extensive reading activity improves reading fluency and comprehension or if, conversely, a high level of reading achievement resulted in more extensive reading activity. The Torppa et al. (2020) longitudinal study followed the leisure reading activity (books, magazines, newspapers, and digital reading) of 2,525 Finnish students both in and out of school from age 5 until they reached age 15. Emergent reading skills were tested at age 5 and reading skills annually from age 7 to 14. Using a random intercept cross-lagged model they found that reading skills and reading volume influence each other. The effect of reading volume on reading achievement emerged in grade 3 and remained a significant factor thereafter. Thus, grade 3 can be considered a critical turning point in a child's literacy development. For children who have not mastered decoding and are dysfluent, reading is a labour intensive, challenging experience which affects motivation to read (Stanovich, 1986; Mol & Bus, 2011), which in turn can bring about *'significant individual differences in the frequency and complexity of reading experiences'* (Van Bergen et al., 2020, p.14) and

subsequent reading achievement. Reading comprehension improvement is ‘predicted by within-individual increases in book reading’ (Torppa et al., 2020, p.876). However, not all kinds of leisure reading result in superior reading comprehension. Book reading was a superior predictor whereas comic books and magazines were not found to promote it. Interestingly, Torppa et al. also found that the ‘early onset of digital text consumption (possibly at the expense of print reading) had a negative association with print reading skills’ (p. 889), converging with previous research (Pfof et al., 2013). In interpreting these results, Torppa et al. (2020) caution that print reading and digital reading differ (Goldman et al., 2012; Leu et al., 2014) and that reader purpose (e.g., for participation in social media versus reading for information) is an important consideration, with different purposes likely to require very different reading skills strategies (Naumann, 2015). Future research should investigate the influence of digital reading volume on reading achievement. Overall, then there appears to be an important relationship between reading achievement and volume of reading, but this influence is apparent only after initial reading proficiency has developed with age 8-9 a critical turning point for such proficiency.

Access to Books

Reading volume and consequently reading achievement is affected by access to relevant books matched to reader interest and proficiency. Children from low socio-economic (SES) communities are less likely to have such access. Allington and McGill-Franzen (2021) note that, at age 17, the gap in reading achievement between students from low-SES families and their more middle-class peers extends to four years. In Ireland, despite concerted policy efforts, the SES differences in achievement in primary school remain high. Shiel, Kavanagh and Millar, (2014, p.xvi), in interpreting overall increases in literacy since an earlier national assessment in 2009, highlight that *‘there has been no real reduction in the gap between pupils in DEIS urban schools and in other school types, except at Second class in Band 2 schools’*. Furthermore, in a review of the DEIS strategy, Kavanagh, Weir & Moran (2017) drew attention to the critical role of motivation / engagement and its link with achievement. When children in 6th class in DEIS schools were asked if they liked school, findings indicated an 8-point achievement gap (about one-half of a standard deviation) between those who liked school a lot (15.3%) versus the children who disliked it a lot (7.3%). A similar question in relation to liking reading found an even bigger gap of 10- 12 points. On average, sixth class pupils who strongly agreed (28.7%) that they liked reading a lot reached national norms (100.5) while those who disagreed (18.8%) or strongly disagreed (8.5%) had significantly lower scores (90.9, 88.0

respectively). A key dimension of reading engagement is access to books both in and out of school that are stimulating and related to students' interests, coupled with choice and control over book selection and reading response (Ivey & Johnston, 2013).

Allington and McGill-Franzen (2021) cite a range of studies (Pribesh, Gavigan & Dickinson, 2011; Neumann & Celano, 2001; Neumann & Moland, 2019) in the US which highlight qualitative differences in school and community libraries located in low- and higher-income communities and access to books in the home. Findings from OECD studies (Evans et al., 2010; Schubert et al., 2010) have consistently found the number of books in the home as significant predictors of student achievement. Access to books mediated family SES and access to a large number of books was associated with twice the advantage of having a father with a professional occupation versus an unskilled worker. Furthermore, children growing up in homes with lots of books completed three more years of schooling compared to those who don't and this held true when social class, parental education and occupation were controlled for. As noted above, similar findings have emerged from analysis of PISA data in Ireland. Pribesh et al. (2011) reported that 'students in most need—those attending schools with the highest concentrations of students living in poverty in the US—had the fewest school library resources to draw on' (p. 143) while Neumann and colleagues found fewer children's books in shops, child care, school and public libraries in low SES communities.

Summer Reading Slump

Davies and Aurini (2013) synthesised the research on summer slump to inform a large-scale Canadian study on summer reading loss amongst children in Grades 1-3. Research cited (Davies & Janus, 2009; Farkas & Hibel, 2008; Willms 2009) highlights that student achievement is predicted by socio-economic status (SES) and that such gaps are perpetuated by key differences in non-school learning opportunities afforded to children from affluent families which support literacy development (e.g., being read to more often, enriched conversations at home, cultural activities and parental help with homework). Additionally, lack of access to books, libraries and cultural activities during the summer months are implicated in reduced learning opportunities for children in disadvantaged communities which has a knock-on effect on reading achievement. Research has quantified the magnitude of the impact of summer learning loss on the reading achievement of students from low-income families. Such students typically lose two to three months of reading achievement (Alexander, Entwisle, & Olson, 2001; Atteberry & McEachin, 2021; Cooper et al. 1996) while their more affluent peers typically add a month of growth. Such losses accumulate over the course of a

child's school life and are thought to exacerbate the achievement gap. Aurini and Davies (2013) reported similar findings in the Canadian study with the bottom quartile of students losing three or more months of literacy which, repeated over three summers, amounts to a whole year of schooling. In contrast, children in the top quartile gained three or more months indicating that they learned at pace comparable to being in school.

In a more recent study by Attebery and McEachin (2021) (commissioned by the Canadian government), participating schools were chosen from a corpus of schools with significant at-risk populations and students performing below average on standardised tests of reading. It was not a representative sample as a further requirement for participation was an engaged principal and sufficient space for the initiative to take place. Methodologically, the study was able to address some limitations of previous summer loss studies. The authors drew on pre- and post-literacy tests scores which were well-timed to be administered as late as possible in June and as early as possible in September, resulting in better data than in other studies. It also included parent surveys on family demographics (37% response rate) and report card information on prior academic performance. As there was variation in participants' SES, researchers split the SES scale into four bands: lowest quartile, low middle, high middle and highest quartile. There was little difference in the 2 middle bands but large divergence between the lowest and highest quartiles. They reported that in June children in the lowest-SES quartile in the study were already 5.28 months behind those in the highest SES-quartile (equivalent of more than half a school year advantage) and with summer loss they began the next school year over 7 months behind. Similarly, the 3rd quartile was ahead by 2.3 months and by Autumn had moved to 3.06 months, highlighting that the higher the SES the greater the gain over the summer. Weir et al. (2017), citing Alexander et al. (2007) found disadvantaged children to be the equivalent of nearly three grade levels behind their more advantaged peers by 5th grade. Ireland has a similar two-month summer vacation to Canada so it is likely that Irish children in low-SES communities experience similar academic loss, unless efforts are made to mitigate against such loss. Kim and Quinn (2013 cited in Weir et al., 2017) found the largest effect sizes were associated with the most resource-intensive classroom-based interventions (i.e. those with 13 children or fewer, those with 4 to 8 hours daily instructional time, and those with 70 to 175 hours total programme time). Allington and McGill-Franzen (2020) took a different approach and highlighted initiatives which have sought to address the reading volume and summer slump in cost-effective and engaging ways for students in low-income communities. Research cited (e.g. Lindsay, 2018) reported that book distribution programmes that distribute books at no cost to children and families (e.g. Reading is Fundamental and

Dolly Parton's Imagination Library) have produced significant reading achievement gains (effect size: $d=+0.435$) in rigorous RCTs where books were provided to randomly assigned students and a further significant finding was the increased motivation to read (effect size of $d = 0.967$). Allington and McGill-Franzen (2020) also report on a large-scale study in which they gave children the opportunity to self-select six books to read over the summer and they did not prescribe completion of book reports or the answering of questions when children had finished reading the books. The studies by Allington et al. (2010) and McGill-Franzen et al. (2020) were multi-year studies with significant outcomes which, over three summers, yielded the equivalent of a full year of schooling. They have argued that, should book access programmes such as these be extended to grades 4-8, '*we could eliminate the rich-poor reading achievement gap*' (Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2017).

Changes in Achievement Gaps Over Time

This section addresses some of the challenges faced in reducing achievement gaps between disadvantaged and non-disadvantaged students. A subsequent section looks at effective intervention programmes in oral language, literacy and numeracy.

A study by Judge (2011) examined, first, whether the reading gap widens or narrows for below-average and above-average, at-risk children during the first four years of school; and second, what protective factors related to individual characteristics, the home and the school predict reading achievement over time from kindergarten through the end of third grade. Results, based on data drawn from a US national database that tracks the performance of children from early childhood onwards, indicated that, as a group, low-achieving children made smaller gains in reading than high-achieving children over the first four years of school, after controlling for school- and student-level variables. In addition, participation in centre-based prekindergarten care, as well as more access to books in the home, better interpersonal skills, and fewer poor physical conditions immediately surrounding elementary schools (a proxy for community disadvantage) and fewer minority students attending a school served as protective factors for at-risk children's early literacy development.

Noting rising literacy requirements in pre-school and kindergarten programmes in the United States linked to standards-based reform, D'Agostino and Rodgers (2017) created a literacy profile for beginning readers across six subscales of literacy (letter knowledge, word reading, hearing and recording sounds in words, concepts about print, writing vocabulary, and text-level reading) using a multiple cohort database that contained achievement data for students at entry to first grade ($n = 364,738$) in the same schools ($n = 2,358$) over a 12-year

period starting in 2002. They found that, overall, beginning of first-grade reading achievement for both low-achieving and more typically-achieving students improved measurably between 2002 and 2013, providing empirical support for the growing academic focus in the early grades. However, their findings about the differential nature of that progress for low-achieving students (often including those with low socioeconomic status) compared to those more typically achieving raised concerns about a growing literacy achievement gap in the early grades. While low achievers made good gains on measures of letter knowledge, phonemic awareness, letter identification and writing vocabulary (lower-order processes), thereby reducing the gap with typical students, the gap increased on word reading and text reading level (higher-order processes). The researchers interpreted this as indicating that kindergarten programmes should include both lower- and higher-order processes.

The OECD (2018) examined resilience among disadvantaged students. Resilience refers to the capacity of individuals to prosper despite encountering adverse circumstances including low-SES. The OECD paper defines academic resilience as the ability of 15-year-old students from disadvantaged backgrounds to perform at a certain level (above Level 2) on the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) in reading, mathematics and science that enables them to play an active role in their communities and prepares them to make the most of lifelong-learning opportunities. Using data from the most recent PISA cycles, the paper documented changes in the share of resilient students over time (2006-2015), highlighted the importance of school environments and resources in mitigating the risk of low achievement for disadvantaged students, and identified school-level factors associated with the likelihood of academic resilience among socio-economically disadvantaged students. Analyses showed that several countries were able to increase the share of resilient students over time (Ireland was not included in the analyses), reflecting improvements in the average performance of students, or a weaker relationship between socio-economic status and performance. In the vast majority of education systems examined, the likelihood of academic resilience among disadvantaged students was lower in schools where students reported a negative classroom climate.

Despite evidence that some practices can mitigate the effects of disadvantage on achievement, and, in some cases, raise achievement levels, a number of studies also point to the persistence of achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy at national level. For example, David and Marchant (2015), drawing on the results of the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) in the United States at Grades 4 and 8, reported that, between

2000 and 2013, poverty and race-related gaps for reading literacy and mathematics did not change, implying a policy failure. However, following Berliner (2009), David and Marchant identified six out-of-school factors that limit what schools can accomplish on their own as low birth-weight and non-genetic prenatal influences on children, inadequate medical, dental and vision care, food insecurity, environmental pollutants, family relations and family stress, and neighbourhood characteristics. They also noted that, along with these out-of-school factors, families and communities living in poverty did not always understand or value formal education, and children from such families did not always benefit from formal education.

Although focusing only on NAEP grade 8 mathematics, Bai et al. (2021) also reported disappointing outcomes in relation to reducing the achievement gap between high- and low-SES students. At national level, the SES gap remained the same over six NAEP cycles (between 2003 and 2017). At state level, 34 out of 50 states' SES achievement gaps did not change significantly, 14 gaps widened, and only two SES gaps narrowed significantly. However, even though achievement gaps in general did not change, improvements were reported in the percentages of low-SES students performing at the basic and proficient levels in NAEP. For example, at national level, the proportion of low-SES students achieving at or above basic level increased from 41% to 46%, while the proportion who achieved at or above the proficient level increased from 8% to 12%. At state level, 32 of 50 states showed increased proportions of low-SES children achieving at or above the NAEP basic level, 4 had no change, and 14 showed decreases. Similarly, 43 states showed increases in the proportions performing at or above the NAEP proficient level, 2 states had no change, and 5 showed a decrease. The combination of mainly static achievement gaps, alongside rising proportions of students at or above basic and proficient levels indicates that, while performance among low-SES students is increasing, performance among higher-SES students is increasing at an equivalent or greater rate. The ideal situation is one in which low SES students improve at a faster rate than high-SES students, thereby reducing the achievement gap in the presence of improved performance among low-SES students.

Drawing on data from Growing Up in Australia, the Longitudinal Study of Australian Children linked to Australia's National Assessment Programme – Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN) across years 3, 5, 7 and 9, Taylor et al. (2019) identified four distinct profiles for reading achievement: a developmentally-enabled profile (62% of children), a socio-demographic risk profile (25%), a child development risk profile (12%) and a double disadvantage profile (2%) (i.e., children at risk because of socio-economical and developmental factors). Children with a socio-demographic risk profile were 1.2 years behind

the reference group (those with a developmentally-enabled profile) in year 3, with a growth rate of 0.2 years (per school year) lower than their developmentally-enabled peers. By year 9, these children had an average NAPLAN score of 8.3 years and were 2.1 years behind their developmentally enabled peers. Children with a developmental risk profile were 2.0 years behind the reference group at year 3, with an average growth rate of 0.2 years slower than their enabled peers. By year 9, these children had an average NAPLAN score of 7.1 years, or 3.3 years behind their developmentally-enabled peers. Children with a double disadvantage risk profile were 2.7 years behind their peers in year 3, with a growth rate of 0.4 years slower than their developmentally enabled peers, and an average reading year level of 5.1 at year 9, or 5.3 years behind their developmentally enabled peers. A key finding was that average reading performance gaps (comparing at-risk and developmentally enabled students) increased across grade levels, with the largest gaps at year 9. Another key finding relates to the challenge in supporting children with a double-disadvantage arising from low SES and developmental difficulties.

The complexities associated with raising achievement are again evident in an article on Massachusetts' success in achieving the highest state-level rankings in reading and mathematics in NAEP (Wong, 2016). The article notes that, despite this, Massachusetts continues to experience large achievement gaps between high- and low-SES students. Past and present state officials interviewed for the article indicated a shift towards addressing non-academic needs of children living in poverty, including childhood trauma, dental disease, access to quality health care, and lack of access by family members to jobs that pay a living wage. Such efforts, which typically call for an integrated approach to disadvantage, seek to rectify inequalities in financial and social capital that exist outside of schools, while continuing to focus on raising achievement levels in school settings.

Effects of Interventions to Reduce Achievement Gaps

The studies in this section are based on meta-analyses and systematic reviews of interventions designed to improve the literacy and numeracy levels of students who are at risk of low achievement because they or their families are socio-economically disadvantaged, or because they live in areas or attend schools in areas with high levels of disadvantage (see Appendices A and B). It might be noted that children at risk due to high levels of individual and/or or community disadvantage may also be at risk from home factors such as speaking a language other than the language of instruction/English and developmental delays (e.g.,

speech and language disorders), as well as various health factors, and these all combine in complex ways.

A consideration in interpreting outcomes of studies, including meta-analyses, is whether dependent measures are study specific (i.e., designed by the authors of the study) or more generic (i.e., standardised measures). In general, study-specific measures (i.e., a test developed by a study's authors linked directly to an intervention) would be expected to be more sensitive to the intervention than more generic ones such as a commercially-available standardised test.

Interventions at Particular Grade Levels in Primary and Secondary

Three comprehensive systematic reviews (Dietrichson et al., 2017; Dietrichson et al., 2020; Dietrichson et al., 2021) undertaken by the Danish National Centre for Social Research assessed the effectiveness of interventions targeting students with or at risk of academic difficulties in literacy and mathematics (see Table 2). The reviews mainly drew on studies with a treatment-control design (randomised control trials (RCTS) or quasi-experimental studies (QES) whose outcomes were measured by standardised tests in reading and mathematics). Dietrichson et al.'s (2017) meta-analysis included 101 studies conducted in OECD/EU countries between 2000-2014. Almost all were from the United States with one study each from Australia, Canada, Chile, Germany and Sweden. More than two thirds (68) were reading interventions while 76% of studies employed an RCT design. The review focused exclusively on studies conducted with low SES students at primary and early secondary level both in and out of school.

A systematic review by Dietrichson et al. (2020) sought to assess the effectiveness of in-school interventions targeted at students with or at risk of difficulties in reading and/or mathematics in Grades 7-12. Students with or at risk of difficulties included students with learning disabilities, students lacking family support, students with emotional or behavioural difficulties, and students learning the first language of the country they are living in. The review drew on 71 studies, with the majority (59) coming from the United States. More studies used reading tests (68%) than mathematics tests (32%), and most were based on lower secondary grades (Grades 7-9).

The 2021 study, a comprehensive international Campbell systematic review, included 205 studies conducted in 14 countries (with one from Ireland). The aim of this review was to provide policy makers and educational decision-makers with evidence of the effectiveness of interventions for children with or at risk of academic difficulties in literacy and mathematics.

Unlike the 2017 meta-analysis, only targeted interventions conducted in K-6th grade were included with 70% of the sample drawn from children in low SES communities. Thus, there is some overlap between both studies. The 2020 study, dealing with post-primary only, included 71 studies with low-SES identified as a moderating factor in many of them, and a high representation of low-SES (62%) among subjects studied. Collectively, the reviews sought to identify the types of interventions that schools and local stakeholders can use to increase standardized test performance in reading and mathematics at different levels, including the performance of low-SES students. Where appropriate, they also sought to identify which factors moderate the effect sizes in the interventions.

Table 2: Overview of Dietrichson et al., (2017, 2020, 2021) intervention studies in reading and mathematics

	Dietrichson et al., 2017	Dietrichson et al., 2020	Dietrichson et al., 2021
No. of studies included	101	71	205
Age range/grade level	Elementary (78%); Middle school (22%)	Post-primary (100%)	K-6 (average grade level 2.4)
Gender	Approximated	47% girls; 53% boys	45% girls; 55% boys
SES (students)	Low SES only	62% ‘Low income’	70% Low SES/ 65% Minority
Study Focus	Interventions in school, out of school (e.g. summer camps, volunteer tutoring)	All interventions were school-based, involving children with varying risk levels.	Chn. with/at risk of difficulties; targeted school-based interventions.
Outcome measures	Standardised tests of reading, maths	Standardised tests of reading, maths	Standardised tests of reading, maths

A limitation of the studies, identified by authors, relates to the reliance on standardised tests which are less amenable to change as outcome measures, with the exclusion of studies using other measures that may be of high quality and provide useful information about how interventions affect students. Another limitation is the high percentage implemented in the US, though the authors argue that the main results are transferrable to other countries (Dietrichson et al., 2021). Additionally, though current evidence highlights encouraging examples of school-wide reform interventions (e.g., Slavin et al., 2021; Epple, Romano, & Zimmer, 2015 (charter schools in the US); Fryer, 2014; Bormann et al., 2003), such interventions tend to be multi-

facted in nature making it difficult to identify the contribution of particular components to the success of the interventions. Therefore, such studies were excluded from the reviews.

Instructional Components of Interventions

The studies examined a range of instructional methods utilised in interventions (see Table 3). Examples of interventions included peer-assisted instruction, using financial and non-financial incentives, instruction by adults to small or medium-sized groups of students, monitoring progress, using computer-assisted instruction, and providing coaching to teachers. Some interventions targeted specific domains in reading and mathematics such as reading comprehension, fluency, number sense, and operations, while others also focused on building skills such as metacognition and social-emotional learning. On the question of whether targeted school-based interventions improve reading and mathematics, the authors were unequivocal ‘that average effect sizes are educationally important, statistically significant, and robust’ (Dietrichson et al. 2017, p.243)...while ‘evidence shows that, on average, school-based interventions aimed at students who are experiencing, or at risk of, academic difficulties, do improve reading and mathematics outcomes in the short term’ (Dietrichson et al., 2021, p.4). Effect sizes correspond to around one-third to one-half of the achievement gap between Grade 4 students with high and low SES in the US. While it cannot be said that all achievement gaps would reduce by such proportions, Dietrichson et al. (2020) noted that the most effective interventions in the sample had real and meaningful impacts on the gaps.

The reviews identified that the two instructional methods which schools can implement to reduce achievement gaps for at risk children, that were more effective than other approaches: were peer-assisted instruction (same age peer-tutoring or cooperative learning in pairs); and small-group instruction by adults (groups of five children or less). Both approaches showed robust effect sizes across measures of reading and mathematics. Other instructional methods showed smaller improvements (see Table 3). In meta-regressions where adjustments were made for methods, content domains, and other study characteristics, these approaches had significantly larger effect sizes than computer-assisted instruction, coaching of personnel, incentives, and progress monitoring (Dietrichson et al., 2021). However, progress monitoring that included feedback to learners showed promise with an effect size of 0.32 at primary level (Dietrichson et al., 2017).

Table 3: Average effect sizes for instructional methods (effect size, 95% confidence interval)

Instructional Components	Dietrichson et al., 2017	Dietrichson et al., 2020	Dietrichson et al., 2021
	Interventions in Low SES Elementary /Middle School (<i>Reading and Maths studies combined</i>)	Interventions at Post-primary level (<i>Reading/ Maths studies combined</i>)	Academic interventions K-6 (<i>Reading/ Maths studies combined</i>)
Coaching/ personnel Professional development	0.16* [0.04 - 0.28] (10 studies)	0.10*, [0.038, 0.166] (16 studies)	0.20 [0.08- 0.32] (21 studies)
Computer assisted instruction (CAI)	0.11 [-0.01 - 0.22] (9 studies)	0.17*, 95% CI = [0.043, 0.309] (14 studies)	0.15 [0.09- 0.22] in single method studies; non-significant effects when adjusted for multiple components and study characteristics (28 studies)
Incentives	0.01[-0.02- 0.04] (8 studies which differed substantially to those included in 2021)	0.05, 95% CI = [-0.103, 0.194] (8 studies)	0.33 [0.18, 0.47] (19 studies combined incentives with other methods, in particular small group instruction)
Peer-assisted instruction/learning	0.22* [0.10- 0.34] (10 studies; coded as cooperative learning: peer-assisted learning: pairs/small groups systematic/ structured approach)	0.19*, 95% CI = [0.061, 0.319] (22 studies)	largest effect sizes (ES = 0.44, [0.28, 0.61]) (32 studies)

Progress monitoring	0.32* [0.18- 0.47] progress monitoring included feedback (5 studies)	0.19*, 95% CI = [0.086, 0.290] (19 studies)	0.17* [0.07, 0.27] (19 studies)
Small-group instruction/tutoring	0.36*+ [0.26- 0.45] (< 5 students in a group;; tutoring: 10 studies)	0.38*, 95% CI = [0.211, 0.547] (22 studies)	0.38*, [0.31,0.44] (118 studies)
Medium group instruction	0.24* [0.00- 0.48] (Small group: 4 studies; These groups were coded as small group but exceeded 5 students so were more like medium group size)	NA	0.32* [0.05, 0.59] (18 studies) (0.10 in single component studies)
Summer/after-school programmes	0.03 [0.06 - 0.12] (Summer programme 8 studies; 0.02 [0.06-0.11] (Afterschool programmes 3 studies)	NA	N/A
Other (groups exceeding 5; extra instructional time; modified content)	NA	0.20, [-0.002, 0.394] (12 studies)	NA

Dietrichson et al. (2017) also examined summer reading programmes which typically involved providing books to students to read and work with over the summer (see above). These interventions sought to reduce the substantial summer reading loss experienced by children (e.g., Allington et al., 2021; Davies & Aurini, 2013) but yielded small effect sizes. The interventions reviewed supplied books to students to read and work with during the summer with librarians or reading coaches playing a role in book selection and most included ‘a

structured introduction and evaluation before, during, and after the summer break, for example, by sending out report cards or phone calls from teachers during the summer’ (p.255). As noted above, Allington and McGill-Franzen (2021), reporting on a summer reading programme in the US, highlighted that simply enabling children to choose six books to read over the summer without a requirement to formally respond to the books, had significant benefits for children and mitigated summer loss. The level of intervention needed in summer reading programmes is clearly something that should be explored further.

In addition to exploring methods, Dietrichson et al. (2021) reported average effect sizes for overall reading and mathematics and for component skills in each domain (see Table 4). For the reading domain, all average effect sizes were significant and positive, ranging from 0.20 to 0.32. Likewise, average effect sizes for Maths are all significant and positive though effect sizes varied considerably depending on the particular skill measured, ranging from 0.14 (algebra) to 0.50 (fractions).

Table 4: Effect sizes for reading and mathematics reported in Dietrichson et al. 2021

Domain Reading	Effect Sizes	Content Mathematics	Effect Sizes
Comprehension (n=73)	0.24* CI [0.18 - 0.30]	Algebra/pre-algebra (n=13)	0.15* CI [0.01 - 0.29]
Decoding (n=92)	0.29* CI [0.23 - 0.35]	Fractions (n=6)	0.50* CI [0.15 - 0.86]
Fluency (n=56)	0.26* CI [0.19 - 0.33]	Geometry (n=10)	0.17* CI [0.09 - 0.25]
Spelling and writing (n=42)	0.32* CI [0.22 - 0.41]	Number sense (n=30)	0.32* CI [0.23 - 0.41]
Vocabulary (n=55)	0.20* CI [0.14 - 0.26]	Operations (n=31)	0.32* CI [0.23 - 0.41]
Multiple domains (n=113)	0.27* CI [0.21 - 0.33]	Problem solving (n=17)	0.33* CI [0.18 - 0.48]
		Multiple domains (n=48)	0.28* CI [0.20 - 0.36]
Overall reading	0.28*	Overall Mathematics	0.33*

Effect sizes associated with studies exploring metacognitive strategies (31 studies, effect size = 0.24) and general academic skills (11 studies, 0.21) were also significant and positive, while those focusing on social-emotional skills (13 studies) did not reach significance.

On average, interventions at post-primary level investigated by Dietrichson et al. (2020) had positive and significant short-term effects in reading and mathematics (an overall average effect size of 0.22), with effect sizes ranging from -0.65 to 3.68 , indicating substantial heterogeneity. The average effect size for the limited number of studies that provided longer-term results was non-significant (effect size = 0.05). Interventions targeting fluency, vocabulary, multiple aspects of reading, metacognition, social-emotional skills, general academic skills, spelling, decoding and writing had effect sizes ranging from 0.14 to 0.22, all of them statistically significant. On average, effect sizes based on mathematics were large (ES = 0.34). Small group instruction (ES = 0.38), peer-assisted instruction (ES = 0.19), progress monitoring (ES = 0.19), computer-assisted instruction (0.17), and coaching of personnel (ES = 0.10) had positive and significant effect sizes. Interventions that provided incentives for students did not have a significant effect size (ES = 0.05). The average effect size of interventions that included none of these components, but provided extra instructional time, instruction in groups smaller than whole class but larger than 5 students, or just changed content had relatively large, but statistically insignificant effect size (ES = .20). The authors concluded that the most effective studies had the potential of making a considerable dent in the achievement gap between at-risk and not-at-risk students in Grades 7-12.

Across studies, there was considerable variation in the magnitude of effects. More research is required to understand the substantial heterogeneity in relation to the success rates of the same interventions in different contexts, the design of the interventions, and interventions implemented in countries other than the USA. There is also a need for research to explore the longer-term impacts of interventions (as few provided this information, impacts reported refer to end of intervention only), which would also make it possible to determine a benefits to costs ratio (Dietrichson et al., 2021). While the overall consensus was positive on the potential of interventions to mitigate disadvantage, Dietrichson et al. (2017) highlighted that, even with the large number of studies in their sample, it was not possible to explain why some interventions worked better than others, or the role that local context played in outcomes. They further suggest that ‘the review can be a source of knowledge and inspiration to schools and local stakeholders but it does not provide a complete blueprint for how to increase the performance of low SES students’ (p.275).

Interventions Focused on Universal Provision in Multi-Tiered Systems

Multi-tiered systems depend on high-quality Tier 1 classroom instruction for all children. They are premised on the idea that such instruction limits the numbers of children requiring additional support in Tier 2 small-group tutoring (provided in addition to classroom instruction) and that an even smaller number would require more intensive Tier 3 one- to-one support. Such an approach is in line with current Special Education provision in Ireland (NCSE, nd), and with the key principles underpinning Response to Intervention (RtI, ILA, 2009), an early detection and prevention framework outlined by the International Literacy Association which has at its core:

- Prevention of reading difficulties through the optimisation of classroom instructional programs
- Responsive teaching and differentiated instruction with careful assessment to inform planning and teaching
- A collaborative approach between classroom teachers, other professionals, and parents
- A systemic and comprehensive approach relevant and sustainable to local context
- Further enhancement of teacher expertise in relation to philosophy and intent underpinning new methodologies and evidence-based practices and expertise to adapt as required for specific needs.

Tier One Interventions Focused on Oracy

Dobinson and Dockrell (2021) explored primary classroom interventions focused on improving oral expressive language skills where these skills were the outcome measured (see Kennedy et al. 2022). They cite evidence from the UK highlighting that at school entry almost 8% of children have significant language disorders (Norbury et al., 2016) while for children in low SES contexts up to 40% have been found to have delayed language (Law et al., 2011, 2013). More recently, the impact of the COVID pandemic has been found further widen the language gap with two thirds of primary teachers (66%) and nearly half of secondary teachers (44%) reporting that school closures had negatively affected the language development of children in

low SES contexts, compared to 21% of primary and 19% of secondary teachers of children in non-disadvantaged contexts (APPG, 2021).

Dobinson and Dockrell (2021) confirmed positive and significant findings for the effectiveness of interactive book reading, structured vocabulary programmes, manualised curricula (in some contexts) and approaches involving speech and language therapists, though the latter was based on only two studies. Though the sample was not limited to low SES, 38% of the total participants attended schools in economically deprived areas. Five of the 31 studies in the review evaluated impacts of the interventions in relation to SES, type of setting attended and pre-existing language levels. Three of the studies (Coyne et al., 2010; Gillam et al., 2014; Gonzalez et al., 2010) found that participants with higher baseline language made greater gains than those who tested lower on vocabulary measures. Dobinson and Dockrell. (2021) hypothesise that the so called ‘Matthew effects’ (Stanovich, 1986) are at play here with the ‘word rich’ benefiting the most. Should this be the case, application of strategies at the universal level could actually contribute to a widening of the gap. The opposite effect was found in two studies (Gillam et al., 2014; Ruston & Schwanenflugel, 2010), when the outcome measure was narrative competence, which was a more encouraging finding. Specifically, participants with a lower initial vocabulary score made significant gains in lexical diversity while those with the higher scores did not (Ruston & Schwanenflugel, 2010) and in the Gilliam et al. (2014) study effect sizes were higher for high-risk participants ($d=1.00$) than for low-risk ($d=0.59$) in respect of self-generated narratives. Additionally, Assel et al. (2007), in a study of Head Start classrooms serving at-risk children found that a manualised curriculum achieved significant impact (0.68) on vocabulary in classrooms served by less-qualified practitioners but not in Title One settings (also serving at-risk children when they were served by more qualified staff) or schools located in more affluent communities. Such differential findings warrant further research and serve to illustrate the complexities and nuances required in interventions seeking to narrow achievement gaps.

Tier One Interventions Focused on Reading

The success of multi-tiered systems of support depends on high-quality Tier 1 instruction. Swanson et al. (2017) investigated the effects of such instruction on a range of essential reading skills including vocabulary, oral reading fluency, reading comprehension, phonics or word reading of students in Grades 4–12 in language arts classes or in content areas such as social studies and science. In particular, the review explored the impact of such instruction on children identified as struggling readers for the 10 studies which disaggregated results to allow for

analysis. Analyses were also conducted to ascertain the role (if any) of moderating variables such as intervention type, duration, grade level and research design might have had on the reported outcomes and is the first comprehensive review of Tier 1 interventions for the sample highlighted. The majority of the studies were conducted in grades 4-5 (n=16) and grades 6-8 (n=17) with only six identified for grades 9-12. None of the moderators were found to impact significantly on the calculated effect sizes. Researchers called for longer well-designed RCT interventions and highlighted the brevity of some interventions as a limitation (the longest study comprised 125 hrs., or approximately 17.9 days of school). There were few studies of phonics/word recognition (n=3) or fluency (n=3). Average effect sizes varied from positive to negative and would require further research to ascertain efficacy, though it must be acknowledged that a focus on fluency and word recognition is associated with younger children. Overall, positive and significant effects were found for Tier 1 instruction on comprehension and vocabulary though effects were small (for 70 effect sizes the mean effect size was 0.09 (95% CI [0.03, 0.16]).

Struggling readers within the 10 studies were defined as those falling below the 25th percentile on standardised reading tests, those with low baseline levels or learning disabilities and effect sizes reflect comparisons between struggling readers who received an intervention and those that did not. Effect sizes varied considerably across the interventions (comprehension, vocabulary, multi-component (vocabulary + comprehension) ranging from 0.01 to 2.52. Findings suggest that multi-component interventions have somewhat stronger outcomes and may be beneficial for struggling readers. One intervention in particular - Collaborative Strategic Reading (Klingner et al., 2004) - produced a moderate effect while two others (Swanson et al., 2015; Wanzek, 2014) produced small to moderate effects. Overall, struggling readers in the interventions maintained or improved over those readers who were in business-as-usual classrooms (control groups). Though promising, few effects were statistically significant and furthermore, it is not clear if interventions begin to close the gaps between struggling readers and their more typically achieving peers. None of the studies addressed each of the key reading literacy skills, nor combined writing skills with reading or reported on children's motivation and engagement, all of which have been found to be important in studies focused on improving outcomes for at-risk children. Previous research indicates that up to 20% of learners will require additional support (Vaughn & Fletcher 2012, cited in Swanson et al. 2017), underscoring that even with high-quality Tier 1 classroom instruction, many struggling readers will also need either or both Tier 2 or Tier 3 support to reach their potential.

Puzio et al. (2020) explored the role of differentiation, defined by Tomlinson (1995, p. 80) as teacher commitment to modify ‘content, process, and/or products in response to individual student differences’. They highlight that differentiation within Tier 1 classroom instruction is a contested space in research and draw attention to arguments made by sceptics (e.g., Schmoker (2010) and Delisle (2015, p.36) who has suggested that ‘differentiation is a failure, a farce, and the ultimate educational joke played on countless educators and students’. Further support for this view, is research in the US which has highlighted teachers’ views that differentiation is difficult to implement in the realities and complexities of today’s very diverse classrooms (Loveless et al., 2008); however, several survey studies have found that teachers report differentiating to some extent (Archambault et al., 1995), most often in relation to content and more often for lower-achievers than higher-achievers (Brighton et al., 2005).

Having the expertise to differentiate instruction is a key literacy teacher competence enshrined in the ILA (2000) position statement on the right of the child to excellent literacy instruction and is a key plank of RtI perspectives and multi-tiered systems of support. Differentiation requires high levels of teacher expertise as it comprises a wide variety of practices and programmes for which the general classroom teacher must be aware in order to select approaches responsive to learners’ assessed needs. Studies included in their review were of particular programmes with some targeting either gifted or struggling readers or differentiation in typical literacy approaches such as literature circles and writing processes (see Table 5 for skills assessed and average weighted mean effect sizes).

Table 5: Average Mean Effect Sizes by Skill Achieved in Differentiation Studies

Skills Assessed in Studies	Average Effect Sizes (range of effects)
Comprehension (n=13)	+0.09 (-0.16, 0.84) 80% positive (Significant)
Fluency/decoding (n=4)	+0.07 (+0.02, 0.29) All positive (Not significant)
Letter-word reading (n=5)	+0.20 (0.11, 0.36) All positive
Vocabulary (n=3)	+0.05 (-0.01, 0.10) Not significant
Writing process (n=3)	+0.96 (significant: winsorised to reduce effect of one study)

Two programmes directed at gifted students had strong effect sizes (ICM/WMLA, +0.70/+0.24; CLEAR, +0.84). In describing the kinds of differentiation reported in programmes, Puzio et al. (2020) highlight both content and product differentiation. For example, ICM/WMLA (p.474) utilises *'advanced multicultural literature at least 2 years beyond students' grade level (content). Students also complete graphic organizers that emphasize higher order thinking and reasoning and produce a self-selected research project (product)'* while the CLEAR programme (p.475) *'supports students to read and interpret advanced texts (content). Each unit includes above grade level readings and challenging activities. Students display their thinking with self-selected products, such as poetry anthologies or research projects (product)'*. An example of differentiation for lower-achieving students was the Dyad project which achieved an effect size of +0.20. This is a paired oral reading initiative pairing a higher-achieving student with a less proficient reader. Students sit side by side quietly reading aloud a text that is 2-4 years above the grade level of the lower-achiever. Positive effects were reported for typical differentiated classroom literacy instruction utilising Writing Workshop approaches to writing (+0.96 significant) and Literature Circles (+0.14) approaches to reading (see Kennedy et al., 2022 for a discussion). On the other hand, MAP (Measuring Academic Progress) using a computer software programme designed to produce reports of student progress and support provided to teachers to differentiate skill instruction (e.g. comprehension, grammar) had no effect (0.00). Studies on writing (N=3) achieved significant average weighted effects (+1.19) with one workshop approach to writing having positive effects on on researcher-designed measures.

Puzio et al.'s meta-analysis revealed an overall positive weighted mean effect size ($g = +0.13$; $p = .002$). They also found that when teachers were supported to implement differentiation, students had significantly higher literacy achievement scores, particularly for the letter-word ($g = +0.20$, $p = .014$) and writing outcomes ($g = +0.96$, $p < .001$). Overall, they concluded that, while differentiated instruction is a valid evidence-based practice at the elementary level, it is not a silver bullet and studies varied widely in relation to impact. They questioned the lack of RCT studies in relation to guided reading, a widely used approach to early reading, differentiated vocabulary instruction and studies in middle and high school contexts. Notwithstanding the limitations of RCTs, future studies should include thick and rich data to *'discuss, describe, or explain the processes, problems, or approaches to matching students with different content, processes, or products'* (Puzio et al., 2020, p.486) so that schools and teachers may benefit from understanding the day-to-day decision-making processes guiding instruction and draw on it to effect change in their own contexts.

Fantuzzo et al. (2011) examined the effects of two early years interventions on disadvantaged children's language, reading literacy and mathematics development. The children, aged 3-5 years, participated in either EPIC (Evidence-based Program for Integrated Curricula) or Developmental Learning Materials Early Childhood Express (DLM). EPIC is described as 'unified programme intended to incorporate systematically the components of content, instruction, professional development, and repeated criterion-based assessment' (p. 768). DLM was shown by earlier research to be consistently associated with improvements, compared with local curricula. Over 90% of children in the programmes qualified for Headstart¹ (i.e., 90% were from families whose incomes were below the federal poverty level, or were eligible for public assistance). Children in EPIC demonstrated better mathematics and listening comprehension than children in DLM, while no differences were found in literacy (vocabulary, alphabet knowledge). Across skills, the slopes for the younger children were steeper, irrespective of programme, indicating greater growth among younger children. Moreover, the slower growth rates for older children could not be attributed to a ceiling effect on the assessments. Fantuzzo et al. interpreted the outcomes of the study as indicating that carefully researched early intervention programmes for at-risk children can be effective in improving outcomes.

A meta-analytic review by Marulis and Neuman (2013) examined how word-learning interventions affect young children (pre-kindergarten and kindergarten in the US) who are at risk for reading difficulties, on vocabulary outcomes, which might in turn, impact on their reading achievement.² The researchers reviewed 51 studies with 138 effect sizes ($N = 7,403$) and reported a mean effect size of 0.87 standard deviations, indicating a strong training effect overall on vocabulary. However, effect sizes varied from -0.10 to 2.13 . Children from low-socioeconomic-status (SES) families experienced significantly lower word-learning gains than those from middle- and upper-SES families who had one or more risk factors (e.g., English Language Learner, language delays).

Silverman et al. (2020) conducted a meta-analysis of 43 studies carried out in US elementary schools that were designed to improve students' language, and, by extension, their reading comprehension, sought to answer three questions: What are the effects of

¹ Head Start is a program of the United States Department of Health and Human Services that provides comprehensive early childhood education, health, nutrition, and parent involvement services to low-income children and families.

² This meta-analysis is reviewed in greater detail in the report on early childhood and disadvantage (French, 2022) that forms part of this tender.

language comprehension interventions on K-5 students' language and literacy outcomes? Do the effects differ for particular populations of students? Do the effects differ according to specific intervention characteristics? Silverman's meta-analysis was broader than that of Marulis and Neumann in that Silverman et al. focused on a broader range of students, including those not at risk, and a broader range of language interventions, through vocabulary-based ones were again prominent. The language interventions had positive effects on custom measures of vocabulary, listening comprehension and reading comprehension ($g = 1.17$) but not on standardised measures ($g = 0.03$). While positive effects were also observed on outcome measures of morphology ($g = 1.14$) and on academic language ($g = 0.08$), the number of studies with outcomes on these aspects of language was modest. Non-significant outcomes were reported for measures of syntax and decoding. Delayed effects were positive and significant on vocabulary ($g = 0.73$) and on reading comprehension ($g = 0.35$), though few studies examined delayed effects.

Twenty-nine of the 43 studies focused on K-2 learners, while a majority (26) included high and mid-poverty students. The samples in 10 studies focused exclusively on English language learners. Thirteen studies included students with disabilities, and 11 focused on students considered at risk. As heterogeneity was statistically significant for vocabulary and reading comprehension, moderator analyses were conducted for these outcomes. Studies with higher proportions of students from low-SES families had lower effects on vocabulary outcomes ($g = 0.77$), though average g was significant. Effect sizes for students deemed to be at risk were slightly smaller on custom vocabulary measures ($g = 0.77$) compared with effect sizes across all studies ($g = 0.85$). Multicomponent interventions were reported to have a higher average effect size than single component interventions on vocabulary, while studies that included vocabulary and syntax were more effective where reading comprehension was the outcome.

The key finding, in the context of the current report, is that studies with higher proportions of students from low-income backgrounds showed lower effects. Similar to Marulis and Newman, the authors suggest that more research is required to identify characteristics of effective programmes for this population. Silverman et al. also interpreted their findings to indicate that interventions that target individual components of language and bring them together with authentic opportunities to use language for comprehension and expression may be most effective.

School-Wide Interventions

A well-known whole school intervention for literacy is Success for All (SFA, Slavin, 1987). It was designed and implemented by Slavin and colleagues at the John Hopkins University in collaboration with school leaders in the Baltimore public schools to address the reading development of the large numbers of children who were not performing to their potential. Research indicated that children progressed into senior classes of primary with low expectations for themselves and without the necessary literacy skills to succeed. Success for All has been implemented in many schools across the US and in some international contexts including the UK. A recent meta-analysis of studies (17 studies met inclusion standards) conducted in the US concluded that though there was a large variation in effect sizes across studies (depending on context and implementation quality) but the average effect size was 0.24 ($p < .05$) indicating that SFA was effective for the target population of struggling readers (Cheung et al., 2021). In particular, overall mean effects were greatest for the lowest achievers (0.54, $p < .01$). Twelve of the studies in the meta-analysis are multi-year studies, enabling an analysis of literacy performance in the same cohorts over time; this contrasts with the five cross-sectional studies, which focus on the performance of individual cohorts.

SFA adopts a whole school approach from the outset and will only work with schools who commit to establishing key infrastructure to support implementation on the ground. Such supports include:

- a full-time facilitator (experienced teacher in the school)
- a full-time teaching assistant to work with struggling readers in Grade one
- implementation of the programmed elements of the SFA approach (PreK/K kinder programme, Reading Roots in Grades 1-2 and Reading Wings in Grades 3-5)
- commitment to participate in professional development provided by the SFA foundation (2 days for all teacher and monthly on-site visits by coaches to observe and provide feedback on implementation)
- whole school regrouping for reading for 90 minutes daily.

The theory of change underpinning the SFA approach relies on early reading success in grade one and two with some paired or one-to-one tutoring for children who require greater intensity. In these early grades, the manualised Reading Roots programme is used and places a heavy focus on phonemic awareness, phonics and comprehension using phonetically decodable texts. In addition to reading instruction, access to services for children who have poor

attendance or require social-emotional support is also provided. The additional tutoring is withdrawn when children have achieved to a 2-1 reading level (second grade term one). In grades three to five, schools follow the Reading Wings programme which has a greater focus on vocabulary, comprehension, writing, metacognition and cooperative learning and incorporates trade books chosen by the school. It is an adaptation of Cooperative Integrated Reading and Composition (CIRC) developed by Stevens (1987).

The whole school regrouping for reading in 1st to 5th grade is a unique dimension of the SFA approach. Children are assessed and grouped across grade levels for a daily 90 minutes of literacy instruction with each group taught by members of the teaching staff schoolwide at the same time. For example, a group reading at third grade level could include strong readers from 2nd grade and weaker readers from 4th class and may be taught by the art teacher or librarian as all teaching staff are involved. Teaching of skills is targeted at the reading level of the group. Programme developers argue that this is an efficient use of time and resources and allows for differentiation.

The meta-analysis on SFA (Cheung et al., 2021) includes two large randomised control trials (Borman, 2007; Quint et al., 2015) and the other 15 are mostly smaller scale quasi-experimental interventions. Though SFA is intended to focus intensive instruction on K-2nd grade followed by evidence-based teaching in grades 3-5, the majority of studies (11/17) are focused on K-2nd grade only. All but one of the studies took place in schools with very high levels of economic disadvantage, with at least 66% of students receiving free or reduced-price lunches (n=16), an indicator of low SES.

As noted earlier the overall mean effect size is 0.24 ($p < 0.05$) across all studies but the range varies considerably with a 95% prediction interval of -0.27 to +0.75, highlighting significant heterogeneity. In the first large RCT (Borman, 2007), conducted over three years in 35 schools (K-2nd grade only) the overall mean effect size reported was +0.25 ($p < 0.05$) and +0.22, +0.33 and +0.21 for word identification, word attack, and passage comprehension respectively. However, in the second large-scale RCT study (Quint et al., 2015), involving 37 low SES schools in five school districts (K-2nd grade only) over three years, the children in the treatment school outperformed the control group on phonics skills only. There were no significant differences found for reading fluency or comprehension. However, the lowest achievers did improve significantly on phonics, word recognition and reading fluency but not on comprehension.

In relation to the quasi-experimental studies, one of the early studies of the first five schools to use SFA (Slavin et al., 1993; Madden et al., 1993) found positive overall effects

compared to the five schools in the control group. The mean effect size across all five cohorts after 3 years (PreK-Grade 1) was +0.59 ($p < 0.05$) for all students and rose to +1.17 ($p < .01$) for low-achievers. Students were followed through to Grade 4 (6 years of SFA) with mean effect sizes +0.41 overall and +0.78 for low-achievers reported. Though not included in the current meta-analysis, Cheung et al. also report on a study (Borman & Hewes, 2002) which followed three cohorts of the original five schools (Slavin et al., 1993) into 8th grade when students would have been out of SFA for three years. Lower positive effect sizes were reported and though these were not statistically significant, students were less likely to have been retained at elementary level or assigned to special education classes. Correnti (2009), in another quasi-experimental study (K-2nd grade) involving 115 schools in 17 states, reported a similar but lower overall effect size of +0.43. Other quasi-experimental studies have reported much lower average positive effect sizes (e.g. Munoz & Dossett, 2004: +0.15, 1st-3rd grade; Ross & Casey, 1998) or negative impact (Ross et al., 1995: K-2nd grade: +0.10; K-3rd grade: -0.10). Ross and colleagues conducted eight of the SFA studies on SFA between 1994 and 1999 and reported wide variation of effects ranging from a low of +0.01 (Ross et al., 1996: 1-year study in 1st grade) to a high of +0.58 (Ross et al., 1994: 2-year study in 1st-2nd grade) while Wang & Ross (1999) reported +0.24 in Grade 1 and -0.05 in grade 2). Such variation in programme effects underlies the complexity involved in changing outcomes in high-poverty schools even with manualised and prescribed approaches as outlined in SFA studies. Furthermore, it is notable that the Slavin et al. study (1993) included children who had experienced a language rich and cross-curricular SFA Pre-K programme which may have contributed to the stronger effect sizes while none of the other quasi-experimental studies included PreK. Other factors to consider may include the required daily cross-grade level regrouping practice and the heavy focus on basic skills. Data on effects of such grouping practices on children's motivation, engagement and self-efficacy are not reported in the meta-analysis; neither is it clear how texts could be selected that would be suitable for example, for a mature 6th grader reading at a lower level and placed in a group including a high-achieving 3rd or 4th grader. Such considerations are important given the research on the relationship between achievement and reader motivation, interest, agency, identity and self-efficacy (Guthrie & Wigfield 2000; Vaughn et al., 2020, cited in Kennedy et al., 2022). Studies in the Irish context (Kennedy, 2018; Brozo et al. 2007, 2014) reviewed in Lee et al.'s (2021) systematic review of reading engagement highlight the importance of the affective dimensions of reading on achievement. Kennedy (2017, 2018) found positive links between reading engagement and reading achievement when children experienced a balanced literacy framework with daily time for oral language, reading and

writing. In relation to reading, for children in 3rd-6th grade in three high-poverty schools (Kennedy, 2018), practices associated with increasing engagement included time, choice, dialogic mixed-ability reading groups, building self-efficacy and explicit teaching of vocabulary and comprehension skills (for further discussion and impact on achievement see Kennedy, 2017). The Brozo et al. studies explored reader engagement and achievement drawing on PISA data, with engagement among students in Ireland consistently associated with reading performance, and lower-SES students demonstrating lower levels of achievement. Additionally, in a review of the DEIS strategy, Weir et al., (2017) hypothesised that some of the variation in the DEIS achievement data is related to low levels of motivation and engagement, given the significantly different achievement of children in DEIS schools who report that they enjoy reading versus those who dislike it.

Although not a meta-analysis (perhaps reflecting a shortage of suitable studies), a study by Gallagher et al. (2017) designed to improve students' source-based argumentative writing at Grades 7-10 in high-risk rural schools with high teacher turnover across 10 US states found strong effects of three aspects of students writing (content, structure and stance, though not conventions), following a two-year intervention. Aspects of the intervention identified as contributing to these positive outcomes included professional development for teachers (90 hours over two years), curriculum resources for teaching argument writing, and a formative assessment tool focused on techniques for using non-fiction sources to develop paper-based reports. The outcomes of the study are significant in that it was a randomized controlled trial (school districts were allocated at random to intervention to improve argumentative writing, or to a 'business as usual' control group), and was aligned to the US National Writing Project's College Ready Writing Programme (based on the Common Core Standards). The professional development, which was characterised by high participation rates, involved engagement in activities such as coaching, co-teaching, demonstration lessons, co-designing learning and assessment activities, and analysing student work.

Interventions Involving Executive Functioning

Executive function (EF) can be defined as the cognitive processes (e.g., updating information in working memory, shifting attention, and inhibiting prepotent responses) that regulate goal-directed behaviour, with EF seen as developing throughout childhood and adolescence, and individual differences being observed from infancy through adulthood. EF has been proposed as a mediator of socio-economic disparities in lifelong achievement as well as health (Lawson et al., 2018). These authors conducted a meta-analysis on the relationship between socio-

economic status and EF performance among children. Drawing on 33 studies representing 25 independent samples of children between ages 2 and 18, they found an average correlation of 0.16 between SES and EF (without correcting for attenuation). When only studies with meaningful SES variability were included (of which there were 15), the average correlation increased to 0.22, while studies with multiple measures of EF (6 in total) yielded an average correlation of 0.28. The authors concluded that the meta-analysis supports the presence of SES disparities in EF. They also noted that none of the 25 studies reported estimates of the SES-EF association after controlling for IQ, perhaps because of substantial construct overlap between EF and IQ. Nevertheless, they suggest that, while correlations between SES and EF are modest, small differences in early childhood may have cumulative consequences across domains of development, including academic performance (a phenomenon termed ‘developmental cascades’).

Ellefson et al. (2020) examined the role of executive processes as an underlying mechanism in achievement gaps in numeracy between low and high SES students. Defining executive functions (EF) as the set of higher order cognitive skills including inhibitory control, working memory, cognitive flexibility and planning that underpin flexible and goal-directed behaviour, they noted that EF development is protracted in nature, making it especially susceptible to environmental influence. They conducted a current cross-cultural study that used a large sample ($N = 835$) of 9- to 16-year-old children from Hong Kong and the United Kingdom to examine the independence and interplay of SES and EF as predictors of numeracy skills. Their analyses yielded three key findings: (1) EF consistently predicted numeracy skills across countries and genders; (2) associations between SES and EF differed by country and gender, with UK males the only group showing a significant effect (consistent with a view that educational effects of social disadvantage may be especially marked in males), in a link mediated by general cognitive ability; and (3) associations between numeracy skills and SES/EF differed by country and gender, with SES and EF acting as independent predictors of numeracy skills for Hong Kong participants and UK females, and EF mediating the link between SES and numeracy for UK males, even after accounting for general cognitive ability. Together with previous findings, these results were interpreted as indicating that there are culture-specific associations between SES, EF and numeracy, suggesting that cultural insights may enable policy changes to narrow the achievement gap between children from affluent and disadvantaged families.

As noted above in the account of the systematic reviews conducted by Dietrichson et al. (2017, 2020, 2021), metacognition comprised an important outcome of intervention studies

involving reading development.

Digital Literacies and Disadvantage

Scherer and Siddiq (2019) examined the relation between students' SES and their information and communication technology (ICT) literacy. SES was measured using parents' education, occupation and income. ICT literacy was defined as a concept associated with an individual's ability to use computers to investigate, create, and communicate. More recently, ICT has broadened to include digital literacy. Being digitally literate means having the skills to function (live, learn and work) in a society where communication and access to information is increasingly through digital technologies like Internet platforms, social media, and mobile devices (Jisc, 2016). In education, students as reflective citizens should acquire digital literacy skills to gather, manage, create, and exchange digital information (Fraillon et al., 2014). Scherer and Siddiq (2019) coded the ICT literacy measures by the types of outcome measure (interactive, authentic or static), the skills assessed by the measures (communication, technical skills, problem solving, information, and safety), the design of tasks, and aspects of their psychometric quality. They reported that educational gaps in digital literacy tasks have been researched less often than the more traditional domains of reading and of mathematics due to delays in the development and validation of measures. The findings of studies that were undertaken on this topic are diverse due to differences in SES and achievement measures, educational level of study samples, the design of studies, and sampling strategies among other characteristics. To address these, Scherer and Siddiq (2019) embarked on a meta-analysis to synthesize SES-ICT literacy correlations for primary studies that included K-12 students and performance-based assessments of ICT literacy.

The main findings in their meta-analysis confirm the relationship between SES and ICT. Students' ICT literacy differed between socioeconomic groups, pointing to a gap in the domain of ICT. Despite the hope that ICT, as a relatively young domain in education, may compensate for SES differences, the study found that this hope has not been fulfilled so far and inequalities exist (Scherer & Siddiq, 2019). However, the magnitude of effect between studies varied and the relation between SES and ICT literacy was weaker than those reported in other educational domains, such as mathematics and reading. The findings show promise "as skills assessed by technology with options to actively generate and retrieve information" lean less "on prior knowledge but [on] the active generation of knowledge and its application in problem-solving situations" (p.30). Research on this topic requires carefully designed studies,

clear approaches to sampling, and a focus on applied skills rather than skills that heavily rely on knowledge in interactive test designs. In addition, contextual factors in education are important, given the variability in moderator effects. Equally in relation to education, learning opportunities with interactive tasks and applied skills may reduce the effect of SES (Scherer & Siddiq, 2019).

Steenbergen-Hu and Cooper (2014) investigated the effectiveness of intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) on kindergarten to 18-year-old students' mathematical learning on the population of high and low achieving students and remedial students, in comparison to regular classroom instruction. ITS are computer-assisted learning environments created using computational models developed in mathematics (algebra, basic mathematics, geometry), among other academic fields. ITS often are self-paced, learner-led, highly adaptive, and interactive learning environments operated through computers. ITS is positively distinguished from e-learning, computer-based training and computer-assisted instruction (CAI) due to their adaptability. ITS operate through two loops; the outer loop sets learning tasks adapted to the student's strengths and weaknesses, and the inner loop stimulates problem-solving steps and gives feedback, prompts and error messages. ITS tracks students' subject knowledge, learning strategies and skills, feelings or motivation through student modelling in detail that is beyond human tutors' abilities (Graesser et al., 2011). The findings revealed that whereas ITS had no negative and perhaps a small positive effect on K–12 students' mathematical learning and small to modest effects in comparison to the few studies on homework or human tutoring. However, the effectiveness of ITS for helping students drawn from the general population was greater than for helping low achievers, suggesting a contribution to the achievement gap (Steenbergen-Hu & Cooper, 2014). The findings imply that ITS may not be an appropriate tool to increase attainment for students who are at risk of educational inequality, without making appropriate adjustments.

Teacher Expectations and Socio-economic Status

The association between teacher expectations and student performance has long been a focus of research and analysis (e.g., Rosenthal & Jacobson, 1968; Jussim & Harber, 2005), with teachers generally basing their predictions of student ability and performance on previous academic achievement (Hoge & Coladarci, 1998). Brophy (1993) reported that teachers typically generate predictions for individual students, groups of students, and whole classes. Rubie (2007) reported that teachers' class-level expectations may be more significant for student learning than

expectations at the level of the individual. Weir et al. (2017) reported on research indicating that teacher expectations may be associated with perceptions of students' social class or socioeconomic background. Benner and Mistry (2007) reported that high maternal expectations could act as a buffer against the impact of low teacher expectations, implying that efforts to raise mothers' expectations as well as those of teachers could prove effective in addressing disadvantage.

A recent meta-analysis by Wang et al. (2018) confirmed that teachers tend to hold lower expectations for low-SES students than for middle- or high-SES students. Across 31 studies that were reviewed, only three showed a non-significant effect of student SES on teacher expectations. Based on their findings, Wang et al. presented a 5-stage model of teacher expectations, in which the following sequence occurs:

- teachers form expectations for students
- teachers behave differently towards students based on those expectations
- students perceive teacher expectations
- students' socio-psychological factors are influenced, and
- students' achievement outcomes are influenced.

Among student factors that mediate teacher expectation effects on student achievement are self-concept, self-efficacy and self-expectations, though Wang et al. acknowledged that no single study has uncovered the entire mediating process of teacher expectation effects. In addition to individual students and groups with low SES, teachers form expectations for a variety of individuals or groups with other characteristics (e.g., ethnicity, gender, learning difficulties, self-concept, behaviour, engagement in class), and, in some cases, these overlap with low SES. Finally, Al-Fadhli and Singh (2006) noted a study in which teachers in high-achieving schools tended to base their expectations on student ability, whereas teachers in low-achieving schools based their expectations on student characteristics (appearance, conduct, parent education level (an element of SES), and parental support).

References

- Aikens, N. L., & Barbarin, O. (2008). Socioeconomic differences in reading trajectories: The contribution of family, neighborhood, and school contexts. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 100*(2), 235–251. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.100.2.235>
- Alexander, K.L., Entwisle, D.R. & Olson, L.S. (2007). Lasting consequences of the summer learning gap. *American Sociological Review, 72*(2), 167-180
- *Allington, R. L., & McGill-Franzen, A. (2021). Reading volume and reading achievement: A review of recent research. *Reading Research Quarterly, 56*(S1), pp. S231–S238| doi:10.1002/rrq.404
- Al-Fadhli, H., & Singh, M. (2006). Teachers' expectancy and efficacy as correlates of school achievement in Delta, Mississippi. *Journal of Personnel Evaluation in Education, 19*, 51–67. doi:10.1007/s11092-007-9032-9
- American Psychological Association (APA) (n.d.). *Education and socioeconomic status*. <https://www.apa.org/pi/ses/resources/publications/education>
- Attebery, A., & McEachin, A. (2021). School's out: The role of summers in understanding achievement disparities, *American Educational Research Journal, 58* (2), pp.239-282 [doi/abs/10.3102/0002831220937285](https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831220937285)
- Bai, Y., Straus, S. & Broer, M. (2021). *U.S. National and State Trends in Educational Inequality due to Socioeconomic Status: Evidence From the 2003–17 NAEP* [AIR-NAEP Working Paper #2021-01]. Washington, DC: American Institutes for Research.
- Benner, A. D., & Mistry, R. S. (2007). Congruence of mother and teacher educational expectations and low-income youth's academic competence. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 99*(1), 140–153. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.99.1.140>
- Berliner, D. C. (2009). *Poverty and potential: Out-of-school factors and school success*. Education and the Public Interest Center & Education Policy Research Unit. <http://epicpolicy.org/publication/poverty-and-potential>
- Brophy, J. E. (1983). Research on the self-fulfilling prophecy and teacher expectations. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 75*, 631–661. doi:10.1037/0022-0663.75.5.631
- Brozo, W., Shiel, G., & Topping, K. (2007). Engagement in reading: Lessons learned from three PISA countries. *Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy, 51*(4), 304–315. doi:10.1598/JAAL.51.4.2
- Brozo, B., Sulkunen, S., Shiel, G., Garbe, C., Pandian, A., & Valtin, R. (2014). Reading, gender and engagement: Lessons from five PISA countries. *Journal of Adolescent and*

Adult Literacy, 57(7), 584-593. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jaal.291>

- *Cheung, A. C. K., Xie, C., Zhuang, T., Neitzel, A. J., & Slavin, R. E. (2021). Success for All: A quantitative synthesis of U.S. evaluations. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 14(1), 90–115. Education Research Complete
- Cirino P.T., Child, A.E., Macdonald, K. (2018). Longitudinal predictors of the overlap between reading and math skills *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 54, 99-111. DOI: [10.1016/j.cedpsych.2018.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2018.06.002)
- Cooper, H., Nye, B., Charlton, K., Lindsay, J. & Greathouse, S. (1996). The effects of summer vacation on achievement test scores: A narrative and meta-analytic review. *Review of Educational Research*, 66(3), 227-268.
- D'Agostino J.V., & Rodgers, E. (2017). Literacy achievement trends at entry to first grade. *Educational Researcher*, 46(2), 78-89. doi:10.3102/0013189X17697274
- *Davies, S., & Aurini, J. (2013). Summer learning inequality in Ontario. *Canadian Public Policy*, 39(2), 287–307. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.3138/CP.39.2.287>
- * Dietrichson, J., Bøg, M., Eiberg, M., Filges, T., & Klint Jørgensen, A. (2021). Targeted school-based interventions for improving reading and mathematics for students with or at-risk of academic difficulties in grade K-6: A systematic review. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 12(1), 1–78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cl2.1152>
- *Dietrichson, J., Filges, T., Klokke, R.H., Viinholt, B.C.A., Bog, M., & Jensen, U.H. (2020). Targeted school-based interventions for improving reading and mathematics for students with, or at risk of, academic difficulties in grades 7-12: A systematic review. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 1-52. DOI: 10.1002/cl2.1081
- *Dietrichson, J., Bøg, M., Filges, T., & Klint Jørgensen, A.-M. (2017). Academic interventions for elementary and middle school students with low socioeconomic status: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 87(2), 243–282. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654316687036>
- *Dobinson, K.L. & Dockrell, J.E. (2021). *Universal strategies for the improvement of expressive language skills in the primary classroom: A systematic review* [doi/full/10.1177/0142723721989471](https://doi.org/10.1177/0142723721989471)
- Dyson, A.H. (2015). The search for inclusion: Deficit discourse and the erasure of childhoods. *Language Arts* 92(3): 199-207.
- Eivers, E., Shiel, G., & Shortt, F. (2005). *Literacy in disadvantaged schools: Problems and solutions*. Educational Research Centre.

- Ellefson, M. R., Zachariou, A., Ng, F. F., Wang, Q., & Hughes, C. (2020). Do executive functions mediate the link between socioeconomic status and numeracy skills? A cross-site comparison of Hong Kong and the United Kingdom. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, *194*, 104734.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2019.104734>
- Evans, M. D. R., Kelley, J., Sikora, J., & Treiman, D. J. (2010). Family scholarly culture and educational success: Books and schooling in 27 nations. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, *28*(2), 171–197.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2010.01.002>
- French, G. (2022). *Supporting literacy (including digital literacy) and numeracy in early childhood for those at risk of educational inequality*. Institute of Education, Dublin City University.
- *Fantuzzo, J. W., Gadsden, V. L., & McDermott, P. A. (2011). An integrated curriculum to improve mathematics, language, and literacy for Head Start children. *American Educational Research Journal*, *48*(3), 763–793.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831210385446>
- Frailon, J., Ainley, J., Schulz, W., Friedman, T., & Gebhardt, E. (2014). Preparing for life in a digital age. *The IEA international computer and information literacy study (ICILS), international report* Amsterdam: Springer Open
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14222-7>
- Gallagher, H.A., Arshan, N., & Woodworth, K. (2017) Impact of the National Writing Project's College-Ready Writers Program in high-need rural districts. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, *10* (), 570-595. DOI: [10.1080/19345747.2017.1300361](https://doi.org/10.1080/19345747.2017.1300361)
- Gersten, R., Jordan, N.C., & Flojo, J.R. (2005). Early identification and interventions for students with mathematics difficulties. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, *38*(4), 293-304. doi: [10.1177/00222194050380040301](https://doi.org/10.1177/00222194050380040301)
- Gilleece, L., Nelis, S.M., Fitzgerald, C., & Cosgrove, J. (2020). *Reading, mathematics and science achievement in DEIS schools: Evidence from PISA 2018*. Dublin: Educational Research Centre.
- Golinkoff, R. M., Hoff, E., Rowe, M. L., Tamis-LeMonda, C. S., & Hirsh-Pasek, K. (2018). Language matters: Denying the existence of the 30-million-word gap has serious consequences. *Child Development*, *90*(3), 985–992.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13128>

- Graesser, A. C., Conley, M., & Olney, A. (2011). Intelligent tutoring systems. In K. R. Harris, S. Graham, & T. Urdan (Eds.), *APA educational psychology handbook: Vol. 3. Applications to learning and teaching* (pp. 451–473). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721414540680>
- Hanushek, E. A., Peterson, P. E., Talpey, L. M., & Woessmann, L. (2020). *Long-run trends in the U.S. SES-achievement gap*. IZA Discussion Papers, No. 12971, Institute of Labor Economics. Accessed at: <https://docs.iza.org/dp12971.pdf>
- Hart, B., & Risley, T. (2003). The early catastrophe: The 30 million word gap. *American Educator*, 27, 4–9.
<https://www.aft.org/sites/default/files/periodicals/TheEarlyCatastrophe.pdf>
- Hecht, S.A., Torgesen, J.K., Wagner, R.K., & Rashotte, C.A. (2001). The relations between phonological processing abilities and emerging individual differences in mathematical computation skills: a longitudinal study from second to fifth grades. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 79(2), 192-227. doi: 10.1006/jecp.2000.2586
- Hoge, R. D., & Coladarci, T. (1989). Teacher-based judgements of academic achievement: A review of literature. *Review of Educational Research*, 59, 297–313.
- Jisc. (2016). Digital capabilities: The six elements. Retrieved from https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6611/1/JFL0066F_DIGIGAP_MOD_IND_FRAME.PDF
- Judge, S. (2011). Longitudinal predictors of reading achievement among at-risk children. *Journal of Children and Poverty*, 19(1), 1-19, DOI: [10.1080/10796126.2013.765629](https://doi.org/10.1080/10796126.2013.765629)
- Jussim, L., & Harber, K.D. (2005). Teacher expectations and self-fulfilling prophecies: knowns and unknowns, resolved and unresolved controversies. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 9, 131-155.
- Kavanagh, L., Weir, S., & Moran, E. (2017). *The evaluation of DEIS: Monitoring achievement and attitudes among urban primary school pupils from 2007 to 2016*. Educational Research Centre.
- Kennedy, E. (2017). Transforming literacy outcomes in high-poverty schools: An evidence-based approach. In C. Ng & B. Bartlett (Eds.): *Improving reading in the 21st century: International research and innovation*. Springer.
- Kennedy, E. (2018). Engaging children as readers and writers in high-poverty contexts. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 41 (4):716-731. DOI: 10.1111/1467-9817.12261

- Kennedy, E., Concannon-Gibney, T., & Dwyer, B. (2022). *Pedagogical strategies, approaches and methodologies to support literacy in the primary school*. Institute of Education, Dublin City University.
- Kuchirko, Y. (2019). On differences and deficits: A critique of the theoretical and methodological underpinnings of the word gap. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 19(4), 533–562. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468798417747029>
- Kwok FY, Bull R, Muñoz D. Cross- and Within-Domain Associations of Early Reading and Mathematical Skills: Changes Across the Preschool Years. *Front Psychol*. 2021 Oct 12;12:710470. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.710470. PMID: 34712169; PMCID: PMC8546213.
- Law, J., McBean, K., & Rush, R. (2011). Communication skills in a population of primary school-aged children raised in an area of pronounced social disadvantage. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 46(6), 657–664. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-6984.2011.00036.x>
- *Lawson, G. M., Hook, C. J., & Farah, M. J. (2018). A meta-analysis of the relationship between socioeconomic status and executive function performance among children. *Developmental Science*, 21, e12529. DOI: 10.1111/desc.12529
- *Lee, Y., Jang B.G., & Smith, K.C. (2021). A systematic review of reading engagement research: What do we mean, what do we know, and where do we need to go? *Reading Psychology*, DOI: 10.1080/02702711.2021.1888359
- *Marulis, L.M., & Neuman, S.B. (2013): How vocabulary interventions affect young children at risk: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 6(3), 223-262.
- Mol, S. E., & Bus, A. G. (2011). To read or not to read: A meta-analysis of print exposure from infancy to early adulthood. *Psychological Bulletin*, 137(2), 267–296. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021890>
- National Council for Special Education (NCSE). (no date). The continuum of support. Primary. Accessed at: <https://www.sess.ie/special-education-teacher-allocation/primary/continuum-support-primary>
- National Endowment for the Arts (NEA) (2007). To read or not to read: A question of national consequence, Research Report No. 47. <https://www.arts.gov/sites/default/files/ToRead.pdf>
- National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD). (2000). *Report of the National Reading Panel. Teaching children to read: An evidence-based*

- assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction. Reports of the subgroups* (NIH Publication No. 00-4769).
Washington, DC: US Government Printing Office
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (OECD). (2018). *Equity in education: Breaking down barriers to social mobility*, PISA, OECD Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264073234-en>
- Oxford Primary. (2018). *Why closing the word gap matters: Oxford language report*. Oriel Square/Oxford University Press. Accessed at:
<http://fdslive.oup.com/www.oup.com/oxed/Oxford-Language-Report.PDF?region=uk>
- Oxford Education Language Group and the Centre for Education and Youth. (2020).
Bridging the word gap at transition. Oxford language report 2020. Oxford University Press. Accessed at:
https://fdslive.oup.com/www.oup.com/oxed/wordgap/Bridging_the_Word_Gap_at_Transition_2020.pdf?region=uk
- Oxford Education Language Group. (2022). *How schools are closing the word gap. Oxford language report 2021-22*. Oxford University Press. Accessed at:
https://fdslive.oup.com/www.oup.com/oxed/wordgap/How_Schools_are_Closing_the_Word_Gap_Oxford_Language_Report%202021-22.pdf?region=uk
- Paris, S. G. (2005). Reinterpreting the development of reading skills. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 40(2), 184–202.
- *Puzio, K., Colby, G. T., & Algeo-Nichols, D. (2020). Differentiated literacy instruction: Boondoggle or best practice? *Review of Educational Research*, 90(4), 459–498.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320933536>
- Reddy, L. A., Shernoff, E., Lekwa, A., Matthews, C., Davis, W., & Dudek, C. M. (2019). Coaching to improve teacher instruction and behavior management in a high poverty school: A case study. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 34(1), 14–21.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000302>
- Rubie, C. M. (2007). Classroom interactions: exploring the practices of high and low-expectations teachers. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 77, 289–306.
- Rosenthal, R., & Jacobson, L. (1968). *Pygmalion in the classroom: Teacher expectation and pupil's intellectual development*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Ruscio, J. (2008). A probability-based measure of effect size: Robustness to base rates and other factors. *Psychological Methods*, 13(1), 19–30.
- *Scherer, R., & Siddiq, F. (2019). The relation between students' socioeconomic status and

- ICT literacy: Findings from a meta-analysis. *Computers & Education*, 138, 13–32.
- Schubert, F., & Becker, R. (2010). Social inequality of reading literacy: A longitudinal analysis with cross-sectional data of PIRLS 2001 and PISA 2000 utilizing the pair wise matching procedure. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 28(1), 109–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2009.12.007>
- *Shenderovich, Y., Thurston, A., & Miller, S. (2016). Cross-age tutoring in kindergarten and elementary school settings: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 76, 190–210.
- Shenderovich, Y., Thurston, A., & Miller, S. (2016). Cross-age tutoring in kindergarten and elementary school settings: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 76, 190–210. <https://doi-org.dcu.idm.oclc.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2015.03.007>
- Shiel, G., French, G., Kennedy, E. & McCormak, M. (2022). Outcomes of the National Literacy Strategy in relation to DEIS in early childhood education and primary and post-primary levels. Dublin City University, Institute of Education.
- Shiel, G., Kavanagh, L., & Millar, D. (2014). *The 2014 National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics: Performance Report*. Dublin: Educational Research Centre. Accessed at: https://www.erc.ie/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/NA_2014_Vol1_Final-updated.pdf
- *Silverman, R.D., Johnson, E., Keane, K., & Khanna, S. (2020). Beyond decoding: A meta-analysis of the effects of language comprehension interventions on K–5 students’ language and literacy outcomes. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 55, 207-233. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.346>
- Singh, M. (2015). Influence of socioeconomic disadvantages on mathematics achievement: A multilevel cohort analysis. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 108(5), 347–357. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2014.899956>
- Sirin, S. R. (2005). Socioeconomic status and academic achievement: A meta-analytic review of research. *Review of Educational Research*, 75 (3), 417-453.
DOI:10.3102/00346543075003417
- Sobanski, J. (2002). *Visual math. See how math makes sense*. Learning Express.
- Stanovich, K. E. (1986). Matthew effects in reading: Some consequences of individual differences in the acquisition of literacy. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 21(4), 360–407.
- *Steenbergen-Hu, S., & Cooper, H. (2013). A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of intelligent

- tutoring systems on K-12 students' mathematical learning. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 105(4), 970–987.
- *Swanson, E., Stevens, E., Scammacca, N., Capin, P., Stewart, A., & Austin, C. (2017). The impact of Tier 1 reading instruction on reading outcomes for students in Grades 4-12: A meta-analysis. *Reading & Writing*, 30(8), 1639–1665.
- Taylor, C. L., Zubrick, S. R., & Christensen, D. (2019). Multiple risk exposures for reading achievement in childhood and adolescence. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 427-434. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2018-211323>
- Uttal, D., Meadow, N.G., Tipton, E., Hand, L., Aiden, A.R., Warren, C., & Newcombe, N.S. (2013). The malleability of spatial skills: A meta-analysis of training studies. *Psychological Bulletin*, 139(2), 352-402.
- *Wang, S., Rubie-Davies, C.M., & Meissel, K. (2018). A systematic review of the teacher expectation literature over the past 30 years. *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 24 (3-5), 124-179, DOI: [10.1080/13803611.2018.1548798](https://doi.org/10.1080/13803611.2018.1548798)
- Wanzek, J., & Vaughn, S. (2014). Intensive interventions in reading for students with reading disabilities: Meaningful impacts. *Learning Disabilities Research and Practice*, 29 (2), 46-53. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ldrp.12031>
- Weir, S., Kavanagh, L., Kelleher, C., & Moran, E. (2017). Addressing educational disadvantage: A review of evidence from the international literature and of strategy in Ireland: An update since 2015. Dublin: Educational Research Centre. Accessed at: http://www.erc.ie/documents/edc_addressing_disadvantage.pdf
- Wong, A. (2016, May 3). What are Massachusetts public schools doing right? *The Atlantic*. Accessed at: <https://www.theatlantic.com/education/archive/2016/05/what-are-massachusetts-public-schools-doing-right/483935/>

Appendix A: Search Strategy

Overview –The overarching focus of the search strategy in this section was the development of literacy skills of Irish language speakers and learners, and linguistically diverse learners. The three broad categories of student are; (i) learners of Irish as a second language (L2), (ii) emergent speakers and speakers of Irish in Irish-medium settings (L1), and (iii) English as additional language (EAL) and migrant students who speak neither English or Irish at home.

Research Questions

1. What systematic reviews or meta-analyses have been conducted that are relevant to the area: Oral language, reading, writing?
2. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing reading skills within literacy?
3. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing writing skills within literacy?
4. How can learners in K-6 be supported in developing oral language within literacy?

Key Search Terms

In searching for suitable systematic reviews, meta-analyses and other literature to answer the questions above we searched the following databases using the key search terms described for each database.

1. LITERACY or reading or reading skills or literacy skills or writing or writing skills or dialogue skills or "oral language" (as a Subject Heading)
2. and k-6 OR elementary OR primary (as a free text search)
3. AND meta-analysis OR systematic review OR best evidence (as a free text search)

Reading Comprehension

Oral reading fluency

Reading Vocabulary

Early literacy skills

Writing

Oral language

Achievement

Motivation & engagement

Google Scholar: LITERACY or reading or 'reading skills or 'literacy skills' or writing or 'writing skills' or 'dialogue skills' or "oral language" AND k-6 OR elementary OR primary AND meta-analysis OR 'systematic review' OR 'best evidence'

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "reading comprehension" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "oral reading fluency" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "reading vocabulary" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB "early literacy skills" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills) AND AB 'motivation and engagement' AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

(literacy or writing or writing skills or literacy skills) AND AB "writing" AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or best evidence) AND (k-6 or elementary or primary)

SEARCH 1

Writing skills or Writing ability or Writing development or Writing improvement or Writing instruction or Writing intervention (Title)

OR Writing skills or Writing ability or Writing development or Writing improvement or Writing instruction or Writing intervention (Abstract)

SEARCH 2

S1 AND Meta-analysis or Systematic review

Key Data Sources Consulted

Note: Literature in the systematic review should be from 2011 onwards, although reference may also be made to earlier seminal works. Examples:

- SCOPUS, EBSCO, ERIC Linguistics and Language Behavior Abstracts, MathEduc.
- Google Scholar (to identify articles that might not appear in a systematic review)
- Handbooks in the field published since 2011
- ‘Grey literature’ (e.g., reports published by international and national organisations/governments – UNESCO, OECD, Dept of Education, NCCA etc.)
- International Database of Education Systematic Reviews (IDESR)

Prisma Chart

Screening of Studies on Disadvantage (Literacy and Numeracy)

Educational Disadvantage Interventions: Meta Analyses, Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses (Appendix B)

Article Title; Authors, Year of Publication	No. studies reviewed	Effect sizes (If available)	Foci of Article	Age range / Grade	Findings (also refer to definitions of literacy/numeracy, as used in article/report)
<p>Allington, R. L., & McGill-Franzen, A. (2021).</p> <p>Reading volume and reading achievement: A review of recent research.</p> <p><i>Reading Research Quarterly, 56</i>(S1), pp. S231–S238 doi:10.1002/rrq.404</p>	<p>Review of the role of reading volume in reading achievement</p> <p>Studies published 2000-2021</p>	<p>Effect size from one study (Lindsay 2018): impact of increasing book access on reading achievement produced effect size of $d = 0.435$ also an impact of increased motivation to read, with an effect size of $d = 0.967$.</p>	<p>Impact of reading volume and access to books on reading development and achievement</p>	<p>5-17 years</p>	<p>A substantial number of research studies have focused on improving the field’s understanding of the development of the ability to read; few studies have accounted for the potential role that extensive engagement in the act of reading might play in the development of reading proficiency.</p> <p>Many views on the role, if any, that extensive reading plays in reading development. Research since 2000, shows evidence that reading volume plays a role in reading development now seems clearer.</p> <p>Recent developments in the research methodologies that might be used to examine any relation between reading volume and reading achievement have provided new opportunities not available earlier when the earlier correlational studies were completed.</p>
<p>Cheung, A. C. K., Xie, C., Zhuang, T., Neitzel, A. J., & Slavin, R. E. (2021).</p> <p>Success for All: A quantitative synthesis of U.S. evaluations.</p> <p><i>Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness, 14</i>(1), 90–115.</p>	<p>Synthesis of 17 evaluations of Success for All in the US</p> <p>Rigorous inclusion standards</p>	<p>mean effect size of $+0.24$ ($p < .05$) on independent measures.</p> <p>Effects largest for low- achievers ($ES + 0.54$, $p < .01$).</p>	<p>School wide approach to literacy</p>	<p>Elementary K-6</p>	<p>Success for All (SFA) is a comprehensive whole-school approach designed to help high-poverty elementary schools increase reading success of students. It is designed to ensure success in grades K-2 and then build on this success in later grades.</p> <p>SFA combines instruction emphasizing phonics and cooperative learning, one-to-small group tutoring for students who need it in the primary grades, frequent assessment and regrouping, parent involvement, distributed leadership, and extensive training and coaching.</p> <p>Over a 33-year period, SFA: extensively evaluated, mostly by researchers unconnected to the program. Although outcomes vary across studies, mean impacts support the effectiveness of Success for All for the reading success of disadvantaged students.</p>

<p>Davies, S. & Aurini, J. (2013) Summer Learning Inequality in Ontario <i>Canadian Public Policy</i>, 39(2), 287–307. Scopus. https://doi.org/10.3138/CP.39.2.287</p>	<p>Not a systematic review but focused on summer reading loss; relevant to DEIS Reviews literature on summer reading loss in US</p>		<p>Summer reading loss Canada and US</p>	<p>Grades 1-3 1376 children in 2010 2011</p>	<p>Focus Education policy should be informed by research that distinguishes school-based learning from learning that occurs during non-school time American studies find that socio-economic disparities in learning tend to widen over the summer months, the longest continuous stretch of non-school time. Articles analyze the first large-scale Canadian study of summer learning. Collected data on literacy growth for a non-random sample of 1,376 Ontario children in Grades 1-3 during the summers of 2010 and 2011.</p> <p>Findings Summer learning was widely dispersed with a mean of zero, and equal proportions of children had substantial learning gains and losses. There were strong disparities by family socio-economic status (SES), as affluent children gained literacy while those from poorer families lost literacy. We attributed 25 percent of the gap between the top and bottom SES quartiles at the start of the school year to the previous summer. We discuss implications for Canadian education policy and future research</p>
<p>Dietrichson, J., Bøg, M., Eiberg, M., Filges, T., & Klint Jørgensen, A. (2021).</p> <p>Targeted school-based interventions for improving reading and mathematics for students with or at-risk of academic difficulties in grade K-6: A systematic review.</p> <p><i>Campbell Systematic</i></p>	<p>Campbell Systematic Review 205 studies up to July 2018 (607 identified; many not of sufficient quality to be included in the analysis) 186 randomised controlled trials. 86% from US. 175 (US)</p>	<p>Overall average effect sizes: for reading tests= 0.28 math tests= 0.33 short-term and follow-up: positive outcomes statistically significant (ES = 0.30, 95% [CI] = [0.25, 0.34] ES = 0.27, 95% CI = [0.17, 0.36]), respectively).</p>	<p>Assess effectiveness of interventions targeting students with/at risk of academic difficulties K-Grade 6 in Maths and Reading Student Diversity:</p>	<p>K-6: ages range from 5–7 to 11–13, depending on country/state on average, 45% girls, 65% minority students, 69% low-</p>	<p>Background Low levels of numeracy/literacy skills are associated with a range of negative outcomes later in life, e.g., reduced earnings and health. Information about effective interventions for children with or at risk of academic difficulties is therefore NB.</p> <p>Findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall average effect sizes for short-term and follow-up outcomes were positive statistically significant. Effect sizes correspond to around one third to one half of the achievement gap between Grade 4 students with high and low SES in the US and to a 58% chance that a randomly selected score of an intervention group student is greater

<p><i>Reviews</i>, 12(1), 1–78. https://doi.org/10.1002/cl.2.1152</p>	<p>10 (Sweden) 7 (UK) 3 (Netherlands) 2 (Australia) 2 (Germany) 2 (New Zealand, 1 each in Canada, Denmark Ireland Israel.</p>	<p>Only studies using standardised tests of achievement: reading and mathematics</p>	<p>LD low family support emotional/behavioural difficulties learning new language Students “at risk”/in danger of ending up with difficulties in the future, in absence of intervention</p>	<p>income students. Mean Grade was 2.4. Most studies had a moderate to high risk of bias.</p>	<p>than the score of a randomly selected control group student</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All measures indicated substantial heterogeneity across short-term effect sizes. ● Follow-up outcomes pertain almost exclusively to studies examining small-group instruction by adults and effects on reading measures. Follow-up effect sizes were considerably less heterogeneous than the short-term effect sizes, although there was still statistically significant heterogeneity ● Interventions in higher Grades tend to have somewhat lower effect sizes, whereas there were no significant differences between QES and RCTs, general tests and tests of subdomains, and math tests and reading tests. <p>Conclusions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Results indicate interventions targeting students with or at risk of academic difficulties K-Grade 6 have, on average, positive and statistically significant short-term and follow-up effects on standardised tests in reading and mathematics. ● Peer-assisted/small-group instruction likely to be effective components of such interventions. ● Relatively large effect sizes together with substantial unexplained heterogeneity imply that schools can reduce the achievement gap between students with or at risk of academic difficulties and not-at-risk students by implementing targeted interventions, and that more research into the design of effective interventions is needed.
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<p>Dietrichson, J., Filges, T., Klokke, R.H., Viinholt, B.C.A., Bog, M., & Jensen, U.H. (2020). Targeted school-based interventions for improving reading and mathematics for students with, or at risk of, academic difficulties in grades 7-12: A systematic review. <i>Campbell Systematic Reviews</i>, 1-52. DOI: 10.1002/cl2.1081</p>	<p>71 studies, with 59 from the US, and the others from Canada (4), the UK (3), Germany (2), Austria (2), and the Netherlands (1).</p>	<p>A significant 0.22 (average of short-run effect sizes); a non-significant 0.05 (average of long-term effect sizes).</p>	<p>Impact of school-based interventions targeting at-risk students in reading and mathematics, Grades 7-12.</p>	<p>At-risk students in reading literacy and mathematics in Grades 7-12.</p>	<p>Interventions in reading and mathematics that included small group instruction (ES = 0.38), peer-assisted instruction (ES = 0.19), progress monitoring (ES = 0.19), CAI (ES = 0.17), and coaching of personnel (ES = 0.10) had positive and significant average effect sizes. The average effect size of other interventions that included none of the above components (e.g., extra instructional time, instruction in groups smaller than whole class but larger than 5 students, or just changed the content) had a relatively large, but statistically insignificant effect size (ES = 0.20). Mathematics tests had a relatively large effect size (ES = 0.34), compared with components of reading (0.17-0.50). The authors concluded that the most effective interventions had the potential to make a considerable dent in achievement gaps between students at risk and those not at risk. They called for further studies looking at longer-term effects of interventions.</p>
<p>Dietrichson, J., Bøg, M., Filges, T., & Klint Jørgensen, A.-M. (2017). Academic interventions for elementary and middle school students with low socioeconomic status: A systematic review and meta-analysis. <i>Review of Educational Research</i>, 87(2), 243–282. https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654316687036 RCT: Randomised control trial QES: Quasi-experimental</p>	<p>OECD and EU countries 101 studies during 2000-2014 76% RCTs English, German, Danish, Norwegian, and Swedish were included Canada, Chile, Germany, and Sweden.</p>	<p>The effect sizes (ES): Reading 66 RCTs AWM: 0.09 (SIG) considerable heterogeneity; range from -0.23 to 0.99. 21 QES AWM: 0.18 (SIG) considerable heterogeneity:0.13-0.82 Maths 21 RCTs Overall ES Similar to reading AWM: 0.08</p>	<p>Academic Interventions in low SES measured achievement by standardized tests: mathematics or reading (e.g., Iowa Test of Basic Skills, Stanford Achievement Test, state- and nationwide tests, norm-referenced</p>	<p>Elementary and middle schools included kindergarten up to about Grade</p>	<p>Socioeconomic status is a major predictor of educational achievement. This systematic review and meta-analysis seeks to identify effective academic interventions for elementary and middle school students with low socioeconomic status. RQs (a) What types of interventions can schools and local stakeholders use to increase standardized test scores in reading and mathematics of low SES students in elementary and middle school? b) What moderates the effect sizes of these interventions? Findings ● It is possible to substantially improve educational disadvantage; average ES are educationally important, statistically significant, robust and provide motivation for action. HOWEVER: When it comes to specific interventions a school or a teacher should choose, results provide less</p>

<p>studies AWM: Average weighted Mean</p>		<p>Range: from -0.12 to 1.27 tutoring= 0.36; (36 studies) feedback/progress monitoring= 0.32; (5 studies only) cooperative learning = 0.22) divided measures into post measures (within 3 months after the end) and follow-up measures. (any period longer than 3 months) (only 7 studies)</p>	<p>commercial tests)</p>		<p>guidance. Even in this large sample of studies, it was not possible to fully explain why some interventions worked better than others. Authors believe impact of interventions depends on local context.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substantial variation in effect sizes, within and between components, which cannot be fully explained by observable study characteristics achievement for the target group. There is still much to learn about how to design interventions for low SES student populations; • All components have positive weighted average effect sizes, but many are small. • Some components have large confidence intervals which indicate, among other things, that there are both interventions with large positive effects and large negative effects, • Lipsey et al.'s (2012) metrics, effect sizes: 0.2 to 0.4 represent 13% to 26% of the average yearly improvement from Grades K to 1; 83% to 167% of the yearly improvement from Grades 8/9. • Current meta-analysis: substantial improvements occurred in a relatively short period of time (most interventions were well short of an academic yr). <p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review: focused on standardized test scores; these tend to be less inherent to treatment; However, excluded studies (did not use standardized tests) may be of high quality and still provide useful information about how interventions affect student • All tests included measured knowledge of reading or math, but these have multiple dimensions. By grouping all tests into only two subject categories (necessary), aspects of what interventions were trying to achieve may have been missed
<p>Dobinson, K.L. &</p>	<p>31 studies in 29 papers</p>	<p>Multiple effect sizes for single</p>	<p>Oral</p>	<p>Primary</p>	<p>RQ 1. What does current evidence tell us about the efficacy and the utility of universal strategies for</p>

<p>Dockrell, J.E. (2021). Universal strategies for the improvement of expressive language skills in the primary classroom: A systematic review_</p> <p><i>First Language, 41(3),_</i> 527-554</p> <p>doi/full/10.1177/0142723721989471</p>	<p>Experimental/ quasi-exper</p> <p>6 countries/ 5 languages; majority US (<i>n</i> = 22) and conducted in English (<i>n</i> = 25).</p> <p>Outcome measures: oral expressive lang</p>	<p>strategy interventions and multiple strategy interventions</p> <p>All studies had risk of bias: presence of potentially confounding variables; nature and degree were varied.</p>	<p>language</p> <p>Particularly expressive language</p> <p>Universal strategies in the regular classroom</p>	<p>Aim was 4-11 years</p> <p>But</p> <p>Aged 4-7 only</p> <p>Sample size:</p> <p>40 – 1296; most had 50- 100.</p>	<p>the development of the expressive language of 4- to 11-year-olds?</p> <p>2. What are the strengths and limitations of the current evidence base and what are the implications for future research?</p> <p>Socio-economic status</p> <p>Markers of economic deprivation were confirmed for 38% TP and a further 20% TP attended schools in economically deprived areas (TP= total participants)</p> <p>Overall Findings</p> <p>Indicative evidence for the effectiveness of interactive book reading, structured vocabulary programmes, manualised curricula and approaches involving speech and language therapists</p>
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<p>Education Endowment Foundation (2021)</p> <p>(Government Oral Language Interventions designated What Works Centre for Education)</p>	<p>Review of evidence</p> <p>20 studies: 1989-2017</p> <p>Includes studies where outcome measures were reading comprehension.</p>	<p>Impact rather than effect sizes</p> <p>Impact in: early years (+7 mths); primary schools: (+6 mths for DEIS; +5 non-DEIS); secondary schools; (+5 mths.)</p>			<p>Key Findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On average, oral language approaches have a high impact on pupil outcomes: 6 months’ additional progress. ● Targeted use of approaches may support some disadvantaged pupils to catch up with peers, particularly when provided one-to-one. ● Important that spoken language activities are matched to learners’ current stage of development in order to extend learning and connect with the curriculum. ● Training/PD can support adults to ensure they model and develop pupils’ oral language skills and vocabulary development ● Schools should consider how they will identify pupils that need additional support around oral language and articulation. It may be helpful to focus on speaking and listening activities separately where needed to meet particular needs. ● Some studies also often report improved classroom climate and fewer behavioural issues following work on oral language ● Approaches that focus on speaking, listening and a combination of the two all show positive impacts on attainment. ● Most studies focus on reading outcomes. The small amount of studies that do study maths and science show small positive effects. Language approaches in these subjects may be used to explicitly practice subject specific vocabulary. ● interventions with frequent sessions (3 times a week or more) over a sustained period may have a larger impact, overall. Approaches that are delivered one-to-one also have larger impacts.
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<p>Jacob, R., & Parkinson, J. (2015). The potential for school-based interventions that target executive function to improve academic achievement: A review. <i>Review of Educational Research</i>, 85(4), 512–552.</p>	<p>43</p>	<p>Overall correlations: reading and executive function = .30; math and executive function = .31.</p>	<p>Correlations between executive functioning and reading literacy and mathematics.</p>	<p>2-18 years</p>	<p>Key Findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examined the link between executive functioning in reading and mathematics performance. Using meta-analytic techniques, the review found a moderate unconditional association between executive function and achievement that did not differ by executive function construct, age, or measurement type; No compelling evidence that a causal association between the two executive functioning and achievement was found.
<p>Lawson, G. M., Hook, C. J. & Farah, M. J (2018). A meta-analysis of the relationship between socioeconomic status and executive function performance among children. <i>Developmental Science</i>, 21, e12529. DOI: 10.1111/desc.12529</p>	<p>Systematic Review - 33 articles, representing 25 studies (independent samples) .</p>	<p>Average correlation of .16 between SES and Executive Functioning reported across all studies.</p>	<p>Correlation between socio-economic status and executive functioning.</p>	<p>2-18 years</p>	<p>Article arises from research identifying substantial disparities in EF, arising from differences in socioeconomic status. Included some studies without primary hypotheses about SES. Substantial heterogeneity was observed among studies, and a number of factors, including the amount of SES variability in the sample and the number of EF measures used, were identified as moderators. Correlations increased to .22 when 15 studies with meaningful variation in SES used. Further increased to .28 when six studies with multiple measures of eF used. The authors noted that there were no controls for IQ in any of the studies they examined.</p>
<p>Lee, Y., Jang B.G., & Smith, K.C. (2021). A systematic review of reading engagement research: What do we mean, what do we know, and where do we need to go? <i>Reading Psychology</i>, DOI: 10.1080/02702711.2021.1888359</p>	<p>Systematic review 60 data-based articles in 12 peer-reviewed journals through 2019.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Reading engagement and motivation</p>	<p>Early Adolescent most reviewed</p>	<p>Motivation and engagement play a crucial role in literacy development and achievement. However, the construct of reading engagement has become blurred and ambiguous, both in research and in discussions of practice. This study presents an extensive survey and systematic analysis of prior studies of reading engagement to guide research</p> <p>In terms of the definition of reading engagement, only 42% of the studies explicitly defined the term. Many studies have focused on the behavioural dimensions and antecedents for reading engagement, while others explored reading engagement as an aptitude.</p> <p>Although this review did not support a single</p>

					interpretation of reading engagement as either an aptitude or an event, resulting discussion broadens perspectives for reading engagement research
<p>Marulis, L.M., & Neuman, S.B. (2013).</p> <p>How vocabulary interventions affect young children at risk: A meta-analytic review <i>Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness</i>, 6(3), 223-262.</p>	<p>Meta-analytic review</p> <p>43 papers published between 1994 and 2011, incorporating 51 studies with 138 effect sizes. .</p>	<p>Average effect size of .87 based on Hedges's g. (Interpreted as indicating that gains were large and educationally meaningful).</p>	<p>Focused on effects of vocabulary development on children in Pre-K and K who were at risk of reading difficulties.</p>	<p>Pre-kindergarten and kindergarten</p>	<p>The average effect size for author-designed measures (1.26) was greater than for standardised measures (0.69). Moderator analyses indicated that children from low SES families experienced significantly lower word-learning gains than those from middle- and upper-SES families who had one or more risk factors. However, additional risk factors compounded the SES disadvantage. The sole risk factor associated with lower effect sizes was poverty controlling for all other risk factors. Based on an analysis of subgroup moderator factors, the authors concluded that interventions must be powerful enough to accelerate children's vocabulary growth in order to reduce achievement gaps. The authors noted that longer-term effects of the interventions were unclear, as most measured growth immediately after the interventions only.</p>
<p>Mol, S. E., & Bus, A. G. (2011).</p> <p><i>To Read or Not to Read: A Meta-Analysis of Print Exposure from Infancy to Early Adulthood.</i></p> <p><i>Psychological Bulletin</i>, 137(2), 267–296. https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021890</p>	<p>99 studies There were no restrictions on study design or on participants' language or country, as long as the article did not report a case study and was written in English, French, Dutch, or German</p> <p>Self-report Versus Checklist (authors and</p>	<p>See Table 7 for summary of effect sizes</p> <p>PreK-K correlation between oral language skills and print exposure checklists moderate ($k = 12$, $r = .34$, $p = .001$).</p> <p>moderate correlations: receptive and expressive, .33 and .35</p>	<p>focused on leisure time reading of</p> <p>(a) PreK/K: 2- to 6-year-old children</p> <p>(b) Grades 1–12: 6.2 and 17.5 years of age</p> <p>(c) College/Univer</p>	<p>29 studies PreK/K: $n = 2,168$;</p> <p>40 studies: Grades 1–12: $n = 2,792$;</p> <p>30 studies undergraduate and graduate students: $n = 2,709$).</p> <p>SES/parental education</p>	<p>Focus Examines whether the association between print exposure and components of reading grows stronger across development.</p> <p>Findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For all measures in the outcome domains of reading comprehension and technical reading and spelling, moderate to strong correlations with print exposure were found. The outcomes support an upward spiral of causality: Children who are more proficient in comprehension and technical reading and spelling skills read more; because of more print exposure, their comprehension and technical reading and spelling skills improved more with each year of education. For example, in preschool and kindergarten print exposure explained 12% of the variance in oral language skills, in primary school 13%, in middle

	titles) Matched studies	vocabulary ($k = 4$, $r = .35$, $p = .001$). basic reading skills as well ($k = 8$, $r = .29$, $p = .001$), and the 95% CI showed overlap with the CI of oral language. Meta-Analysis 2: Grades 1–12 Effect sizes between print exposure and all outcome measures ranged between .15 and .45. Meta-Analysis 3: Undergraduate /Graduate Oral language: strong correlates with print exposure ($k = 18$, $r = .58$, $p = .001$); moderate effect: reading comprehension ($k = 11$, $r = .41$, $p = .001$)		levels available only for the youngest group of pre-conventional readers:	school 19%, in high school 30%, and in college and university 34%. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Although instruction is considered to play a main role in learning to read texts with increasing accuracy and fluency (National Reading Panel, 2000), current findings show that print exposure also makes a difference to conventional readers' technical reading and spelling skills. Leisure time reading is especially important for low-ability readers. Basic reading skills of lower ability children in primary and middle school were more strongly related to print exposure as compared with higher ability readers. When low-ability readers have experience with books at home, they practice basic reading skills more, and as a result they become more accurate and fluent in reading text than their lower ability peers who are less exposed to print. The findings suggest that stimulating leisure time reading should be an effective intervention for low-ability readers as is predicted by the self-teaching hypothesis (Share, 1995). Conclusion We conclude that shared book reading to pre-conventional readers may be part of a continuum of out-of-school reading experiences that facilitate children's language, reading, and spelling achievement throughout their development.
Murphy, P. K., Wilkinson, I. A., Soter, A. O., Hennessey, M. N., & Alexander, J. F. Examining the effects of	42 studies Meta-analysis	Multiple effect sizes reported throughout	Oral language and discussion-based approaches to reading	Range of ages Most were 4 th to 6 th	To date (2009) no syntheses have quantitatively reviewed the vast body of literature on classroom discussions for their effects on students' comprehension and learning. Current meta-analysis of empirical studies was

<p>classroom discussion on students' comprehension of text: A meta-analysis</p> <p><i>Journal of Educational Psychology, 101(3), 740</i></p>			<p>comprehension on thinking and reasoning</p>	<p>grade</p>	<p>conducted to examine evidence of the effects of classroom discussion on measures of teacher and student talk and on individual student comprehension and critical-thinking and reasoning outcomes.</p> <p>Results revealed that several discussion approaches produced strong increases in the amount of student talk and concomitant reductions in teacher talk, as well as substantial improvements in text comprehension.</p> <p>Few approaches to discussion were effective at increasing students' literal or inferential comprehension and critical thinking and reasoning.</p> <p>Effects were moderated by study design, the nature of the outcome measure, and student academic ability.</p>
<p>Puzio, K., Colby, G. T., & Algeo-Nichols, D. (2020).</p> <p>Differentiated literacy instruction: Boondoggle or best practice? <i>Review of Educational Research, 90(4), 459–498.</i> https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320933536</p>	<p>Meta-analysis /synthesis 20 years of literacy research: 18 studies with 25 study cohorts.</p>	<p>overall weighted mean effect size (g): +0.13 (p = .002)</p> <p>88% of individual point estimates were positive.</p>	<p>effects of Tier 1 differentiation, provided by general education classroom teachers on literacy outcomes</p>	<p>Elementary</p>	<p>Key Question Given the academic, cultural, and linguistic diversity in any classroom or school, how can a classroom teacher best support the learning of every student simultaneously?</p> <p>Findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distinguishes between designed differentiation (pre-planned) and interactional differentiation (on the fly); authors provide multiple examples of content, process, and product differentiation in the context of literacy instruction for the general classroom and gifted and struggling students; • Positive effect sizes for a range of literacy outcomes and projects (fluency, decoding, letter-word reading, vocabulary, comprehension, and writing achievement). <p>Overall</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall, findings indicate that differentiated literacy instruction is an effective evidence-based practice at the elementary level.

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When teachers are supported to differentiate instruction, students have significantly higher literacy achievement scores, particularly for letter-word ($g = +0.20$, $p = .014$) and writing outcomes ($g = +0.96$, $p < .001$). • Most successful programs: very different approaches to differentiation: individualization, choice, and an alternate curriculum. • Across the studies, there was an alarming lack of information about the decision-making processes used to guide differentiation and there were no experimental or quasi-experimental studies on guided reading. This review may be helpful as schools clarify their vision for literacy differentiation.
<p>Scherer, R., & Siddiq, F. (2019).</p> <p>The relation between students' socioeconomic status and ICT literacy: Findings from a meta-analysis. <i>Computers & Education</i>, 138, 13–32.</p>	<p>Meta-analysis</p> <p>11 studies involving students in K-12, that had 32 independent samples and reported 75 correlation coefficients.</p>	<p>Average overall correlation of 0.21 between SES and ICT literacy, described as positive, significant and small.</p>	<p>Examined associations between SES and ICT literacy.</p>	<p>K-12,</p>	<p>This overall correlation varied between studies and was moderated by the type of SES measure, the type of ICT literacy assessment, the broad categories of ICT skills assessed, the assessment of test fairness, and the sampling procedure employed. The findings suggest that students' ICT literacy differs between socioeconomic status groups, thus pointing to a gap in the domain of ICT. The authors noted that the relation between SES and ICT literacy was weaker than those reported in other educational domains, such as mathematics and reading. Nevertheless, the outcomes indicated gaps in ICT literacy that need to be addressed, especially among low-SES students.</p>

<p>Shenderovich, Y., Thurston, A., & Miller, S. (2016). Cross-age tutoring in kindergarten and elementary school settings: A systematic review and meta-analysis.</p> <p><i>International Journal of Educational Research</i>, 76, 190–210</p>	<p>Systematic Review 15 studies involving 5-11 year olds taught by non-professional tutors (e.g., classmates, volunteers)</p>	<p>Small but significant effect sizes on composite measures of reading, decoding and comprehension, but not on other reading subskills or mathematics.</p>	<p>Examined effects of tutoring by non-professionals on the literacy and numeracy skills of at-risk students aged 5-11.</p>	<p>5-11 year olds and their non-professional tutors.</p>	<p>The number of studies included was small (15), from an initial pool of 11,564 titles. Questions regarding study limitations, lack of cost information, heterogeneity of effects, and the relatively small number of studies that have used a randomized controlled trial design led the authors to conclude that the evidence base is not strong. Subgroup analyses of included studies indicated that highly-structured reading programmes were of more benefit than those that were more loosely-structured. The authors called for improved research (e.g., large-scale replication trials using factorial designs, reliable outcome measures, process evaluations and logic models).</p>
<p>Silverman, R.D., Johnson, E., Keane, K., & Khanna, S. (2020). Beyond decoding: A meta-analysis of the effects of language comprehension interventions on K–5 students’ language and literacy outcomes</p> <p><i>Reading Research Quarterly</i>, 55, 207-233. https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.346</p> <p>DOI: 10.1037/a0032447</p>	<p>Meta-analysis 43 language intervention studies in US elementary schools, covering students in grades K-5. Examined whether effects varied, based on participant and intervention characteristics.</p>	<p>Effects were large and significant for custom measure of vocabulary ($g = 0.85, p < .01$), though not for standardised measures ($g = 0.03, p = .17$). Modest effects were reported for listening comprehension ($g = .10, p < .01$) and for reading comprehension ($g = .19, p < .01$), though effect sizes were significant for custom measures (0.19 and 0.68 respectively) rather than standardised ones (0.03 and 0.08).</p>	<p>Examined impact of language comprehension (vocabulary and semantics, morphology and syntax) on students in Grades K to 5 on a range of outcome measures related to literacy.</p>	<p>Children in Grades K-5 in elementary schools (Authors noted more studies involving K-3 students, than studies involving higher grade levels).</p>	<p>The authors also found positive and significant effect on morphology ($g = 1.14, p < .01$) and academic language ($g = 0.08, p = .04$), but urged caution in interpreting these data as too few studies were available. They reported no effects on syntax ($g = 0.01, p = .99$) or decoding ($g = 0.05, p = .73$). Delayed effects were positive and statistically significant on vocabulary ($g = 0.73, p < .01$) and reading comprehension ($g = 0.35, p < .01$), though, again, these were based on a limited number of studies. The authors noted that interventions including attention to both vocabulary and morphology showed positive effects on vocabulary while interventions combining syntax and vocabulary showed positive effects on reading comprehension. They speculated that interventions targeting language components and bringing them together with opportunities to use language for comprehension and expression may be most effective. The authors concluded that more research is needed on how best to support language comprehension for students from low-income backgrounds, and how interventions can be optimised to support generalizable language and literacy outcomes.</p>

		No effects were seen on syntax or decoding.			
<p>Steenbergen-Hu, S., & Cooper, H. (2013).</p> <p>A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of intelligent tutoring systems on K-12 students' mathematical learning.</p> <p><i>Journal of Educational Psychology, 105(4), 970–987.</i></p>	<p>Meta-analysis</p> <p>26 reports containing 34 independent samples were used to examine impact of intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) on mathematics performance.</p>	<p>ITS had a small positive effect on K–12 students' mathematical learning, compared with classroom learning, with the average effect sizes ranging from $g = 0.01$ to $g = 0.09$. ITS had small to modest effects compared with homework or human tutoring, based on a small number of studies.</p>	<p>Looked at effects of ITS on mathematics performance (defined as standardized test scores, modified standardized test scores, course grades, or scores on tests developed by researchers)</p>	<p>Children in Grades K-12, including high achievers, low achievers, and remedial students. Studies involving only students with learning disabilities or social/emotional disorders were not included.</p>	<p>Effects of ITS were greater when the interventions lasted for less than a school year than when they lasted for 1 school year or longer. Effectiveness of ITS for helping students drawn from the general population was greater than for helping low achievers. The authors interpreted this as drawing attention to whether computerized learning might contribute to the achievement gap between students with different achievement levels and aptitudes. The authors conclude that, 'for students who are motivated and can self-regulate learning, ITS might be effective supplements to regular class instruction. However, ITS may not be efficient tools to boost low achievers' or at-risk students' achievement" (p. 985).</p>
<p>Swanson, E., Stevens, E., Scammacca, N., Capin, P., Stewart, A., & Austin, C. (2017).</p> <p>The impact of Tier 1 reading instruction on reading outcomes for students in Grades 4-12: A meta-analysis.</p> <p><i>Reading & Writing, 30(8), 1639–1665.</i></p>	<p>40 studies in 37 publications from 2000-2015 20 experimental and 20 quasi-experimental</p>	<p>Standardized outcome measures: 70 effect sizes from 25 studies.</p> <p>Mean effect size for these studies was 0.09 (SE = .03, $p = .008$, 95% CI [0.03, 0.16]),</p>	<p>Evidence on effects of Tier 1 reading instruction on reading outcomes and a synthesis of effects for students identified as struggling</p>	<p>Grades 4-12</p>	<p>Focus Understanding the efficacy of evidence-based reading practices delivered in the Tier 1 (i.e. general classroom) setting is critical to successful implementation of multi-tiered systems, meeting a diverse range of student learning needs, and providing high quality reading instruction across content areas.</p> <p>RQS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the effects of Tier 1 reading instruction on the reading outcomes (i.e., reading, vocabulary, oral reading fluency, reading comprehension, phonics or word reading) of students in Grades 4–12?

			readers		<p>2. What variables (e.g., intervention type, hours of treatment, grade level, research design) moderate the effect of Tier 1 instruction on reading outcomes for this population?</p> <p>3. What are the effects of Tier 1 reading instruction on the reading outcomes of struggling readers in Grades 4–12?</p> <p>Overall</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant, positive effects: Tier 1 reading instruction on comprehension, vocabulary • Synthesis for struggling readers: they maintained or improved reading comprehension over struggling readers receiving typical instruction.
<p>Wang, S., Rubie-Davies, C.M., & Meissel, K. (2018).</p> <p>A systematic review of the teacher expectation literature over the past 30 years.</p> <p><i>Educational Research and Evaluation, 24 (3-5), 124-179, DOI: 10.1080/13803611.2018.1548798</i></p>	<p>Systematic Review (Narrative Synthesis)</p> <p>Identified broad themes in the research literature on teacher expectations between 1989 and 2018. They review was based on 144 studies.</p>	<p>Effect sizes were not reported. Four themes were identified: (1) influential factors on teacher expectations; (2) mediation mechanism of teacher expectations; (3) moderating factors of teacher expectation effects; (4) teacher expectation effects on student socio-psychological, behavioural, and achievement outcomes</p>	<p>Recent avenues of research in the teacher expectations literature (1989-2018).</p>	<p>Teachers of students in Kindergarten to College level, with a majority of students conducted at primary/elementary level. Subject areas included language arts/literacy, mathematics, GPA, drop out and attending college,</p>	<p>On the whole, most studies were regarded as confirming earlier research findings regarding the 4 identified themes, although there were some studies that found results contradicting earlier work. New research topics and directions raised in the past 3 decades were identified in this review, especially regarding the mediation of teacher expectations and the socio-psychological and behavioural outcomes of the expectation effects. In terms of implications, the authors argue that teachers could be made aware that some of their students might be underestimated only because of the students' learning disability status or their families' social and economic positions. They further argued that the review could inform teachers on how to communicate expectations to students, and they noted that teachers should understand that their expectations can exert important influences on how their students see themselves, where the students believe they could achieve, and what the students could achieve eventually. The authors identified a need for further research on the relationships between teacher expectations, student perceptions of teacher expectations and student achievement. They also called for more</p>

					work on possible mediating effects of teachers' differential behaviours between teacher expectations and student achievement outcomes
<p>Wanzek, J., Vaughn, S., Scammacca, N., Gatlin, B., Walker, M.A. & Capin, P. (2016).</p> <p>Meta-analyses of the effects of Tier 2 type reading interventions in Grades K-3.</p> <p><i>Educational Psychology Review</i> 28:551–576. doi: 10.1007/s10648-015-9321-7</p>	<p>Authors conducted four meta-analyses on 72 studies.</p>	<p>(1) standardized foundational skill measures (mean ES=0.54),</p> <p>(2) not-standardised foundational skill measures (mean ES=0.62),</p> <p>(3) standardised language/ comprehension measures (mean ES= 0.36),</p> <p>(4) non-standardised comprehension measures (mean ES=1.02).</p>	<p>Effects of tier 2 intervention</p>	<p>K-3rd Grade 19 (K) 27 (Grade 1) 7 (Grade 2) 2 (Grade 3) 17 (multi-grade) majority (58 %) of studies examined low SES populations</p>	<p>Focus Meta-analysis extends previous work on Tier 3 type reading interventions (Wanzek & Vaughn, 2007; Wanzek et al., 2013) to Tier 2 type interventions. It examined a non-overlapping set of studies addressing the effects of less extensive reading interventions for students with or at risk for reading difficulties in Grades K-3. Tier 2 type, interventions provide additional instruction for students who are not making adequate progress within the core, or Tier 1 type, instruction; they are preventative in nature in the early grades.</p> <p>RQ</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the effects of less extensive reading interventions (i.e., 15–99 sessions) for students with reading difficulties? 2. What features (e.g., focus of instruction, group size) of these less extensive interventions are related to student outcomes? <p>Findings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It examined the overall effects of these interventions on students' foundational skills, language, and comprehension as well as the intervention features that may be associated with improved outcomes. ● Small, medium and large effect sizes found. Larger effects on non-standardised measures. Highest effects for foundational reading skills. ● There were no differences in effects related to intervention type, instructional group size, grade level, intervention implementer, or the number of intervention hours.

Additional Sources (Grey Literature)					
<p>Ellefson, M. R., Zachariou, A., Ng, F. F., Wang, Q., & Hughes, C. (2020).</p> <p>Do executive functions mediate the link between socioeconomic status and numeracy skills? A cross-site comparison of Hong Kong and the United Kingdom</p>	<p>Single Research Study</p> <p>Examined the independence and interplay of SES and Executive Functions as predictors of numeracy skills.</p>	<p>n/a</p>	<p>Associations between executive functioning, socioeconomic status and numeracy performance.</p>	<p>Sample (N = 835) of 9- to 16-year-old children from Hong Kong and the United Kingdom</p>	<p>Analyses yielded three key findings: (a) EFs consistently predicted numeracy skills across sites and genders; (b) associations between SES and EFs differed by site and gender; and (c) associations between numeracy skills and SES/EFs differed by site and gender. Authors concluded that, along with previous findings, our results suggest culture-specific associations among SES, EFs, and numeracy, indicating that cultural insights may enable impactful shifts in public policy to narrow the achievement gap between children from affluent and disadvantaged families.</p>
<p>Fien, H., Chard, J. D. & Baker, D. (2020)</p> <p>Can the Evidence Revolution and Multi-Tiered Systems of Support Improve Education Equity and Reading Achievement?</p> <p><i>Reading Research Quarterly, 56 (S1) pp. S105–S118 doi:10.1002/rrq.391</i></p>	<p>Review</p>	<p>n/a</p>	<p>Evidence based Revolution and Multi-Tiered Systems of Support - Reading</p>	<p>Multiple</p>	<p>Situates education, and the science of reading (SOR) in the midst of a broad, evidence-based revolution involving an array of disciplines focused on improving the health and well-being of individuals and populations.</p> <p>Low/stagnant levels of reading proficiency, massive reading disparities, and a robust SOR knowledge base suggest that the withholding of evidence-based practices in schools differentially harms students of Colour, from poor families, English learners, and students with disabilities. Acknowledges simply expecting greater use of evidence-based reading practices will not suffice. Presents a framework where practitioners/ policymakers could continue to gain better and easier access to the SOR knowledge base and evidence-based reading practices</p> <p>Argues how schools are organized to provide reading instruction is also a key consideration in efforts to expand the use of evidence-based practices.</p> <p>Makes the case for use of comprehensive multi-tiered systems of support approaches in reading</p> <p>Much is not known about how to scale the use of effective practices, scaling efforts themselves represent opportunities to generate new SOR knowledge on both the supply and demand sides.</p>

					Argues that SOR knowledge base is a dynamic and constantly emerging phenomenon, rather than a static repository waiting to be accessed and used.
<p>Fantuzzo, J. W., Gadsden, V. L., & McDermott, P. A (2011) An integrated curriculum to improve Mathematics, Language and Literacy for Head Start Children <i>American Educational Research Journal</i>, 48(3), 763–793. https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831210385446</p>	Field trial		Comparison of efficacy of EPIC programme VS DLM programme	Seventy Head Start classrooms (N = 1,415 children) 4-5 year olds	<p>Reports on the development and field trial of an integrated Head Start curriculum (Evidence-Based Program for Integrated Curricula [EPIC]) focusing on comprehensive mathematics, language, and literacy skills. Comparison study (participants randomly assigned) between EPIC and the Developmental Learning Materials Early Childhood Express; curricula implemented as standalone programs.</p> <p>EPIC included instruction in mathematics, language, literacy, and approaches to learning skills; formative assessment; and a learning community for teachers.</p> <p>Multilevel growth modelling through four direct assessments revealed significant main effects and growth rates in mathematics and listening comprehension favouring EPIC, controlling for demographics and special needs and language status. Both programmes produced significant growth rates in literacy.</p>
<p>Foorman, B. R., Herrera, S. & Dombek, J. (2018). The relative impact of aligning Tier 2 intervention materials with classroom core reading materials in Grades K-2nd. <i>Elementary School Journal</i>, 118(3), 477-504. DOI: 0013-5984/2018/11803-0006\$10.00</p>	RCT	relatively few, small impacts (effect sizes ranging from .18 to .38)	compared 2 early literacy interventions— one using stand-alone materials; one using materials embedded in the existing core reading/ language arts program m.	K-2 nd 55 low-performing schools across Florida 3,447 students <below the 30 th percentile: vocabulary reading-related skills	<p>Focus Comparison of 2 interventions seeking to align Tier 2 intervention with regular classroom instruction</p> <p>Findings Both interventions were implemented with fidelity for 45 minutes daily for 27 weeks in small groups of 4 students (or 5 in grade 2). The standalone intervention significantly improved grade 2 spelling outcomes relative to the embedded intervention; Some differential impacts due to cohort and baseline and, in kindergarten, to English-learner status. On average, students in schools in both interventions showed similar improvement in reading and language outcomes and similar percentile gains to those in recent systematic reviews.</p>

					Conclusion Authors conclude that small effect sizes raise doubt about the significance of this study
Gallagher, H.A., Arshan, N., & Woodworth, K. (2017) Impact of the National Writing Project's College-Ready Writers Program in high-need rural districts. <i>Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness</i> , 10(3), 570-595 https://doi.org/10.1080/19345747.2017.1300361	RCT District-randomized controlled trial of the National Writing Project's College-Ready Writers Program (CRWP), implemented in high-need rural districts in 10 US states. Districts randomly assigned to control or writing intervention conditions.	Data sources: monitoring of PD (monitoring, interviews, observations); variation in PD among participant teachers; changes in teachers' classroom instruction; and students' writing performance (on demand prompt). Average effect on students' writing; 0.20.	Evaluation of impact of a programme to improve students' writing with a strong emphasis on the impact of teacher PD. Focus was on argumentative writing and writing using source materials.	1,881 treatment students and 2175 control students in grades 7 – 10 (year 1 of 2) with 65% of both groups in receipt of free school meals. Also included 329 teachers at baseline, though there was significant attrition in year 2.	According to the authors, the intervention had positive, statistically significant, and robust effects on the quality of treatment students' writing in three of the four attributes measured by the AWC-SBA (i.e., content, structure and stance, but not conventions). Improvements were attributed to: (a) formative assessment tools that highlighted key qualities of effective argument writing and helped teachers find evidence for whether their students' writing had those qualities; (b) curricular resources for teachers to plan and deliver instruction on key skills; and (c) professional development that supported teachers in transferring new instructional ideas into their classrooms. The study was interpreted as adding rigorous experimental evidence to a body of literature that indicates that professional development that addresses more than one aspect of instructional capacity—in this case, teacher knowledge and skill, instructional materials, and formative assessment tools—can lead to meaningful student learning.
Oracy All-Party Parliamentary Group. (2020). <i>Speak for change: Initial findings and recommendations from the Oracy All-Party Parliamentary Group Inquiry.</i> https://d5119182-bdac-43d5-be55-e817e7736e5b.filesusr.co	Review of Evidence (linked to Sutton Trust Review) for system action in relation to Oracy				Key recommendations DfE should develop non-statutory guidance to support schools to embed the statutory spoken language requirements within the National Curriculum which sets out clear expectations for oracy teaching and learning, including a learning progression for students. DfE should include evidence on the role of oracy in closing the attainment gap and improving outcomes for pupils from the most disadvantaged backgrounds

<p>m/ugd/2c80ff_33e3208ce4dd4764b154682488c53ef7.pdf</p>					<p>in guidance for schools on how to use the pupil premium and catch-up funding. DfE should recognise the ongoing importance of oracy and language development beyond early years by extending catch-up investment for oral language and fully integrating oracy into all policies relating to literacy, pupil premium, social mobility, area-based initiatives, tch development and school improvement. Ofsted should develop training and guidance for inspectors on how to inspect schools' oracy provision and make clear through communication with schools that oracy is valued at inspection Ofqual should reinstate an improved form of the spoken language assessment as a contributory element of the GCSE grading, reviewing the best means of assessing spoken language at GCSE to ensure assessment at this vital stage is fit for purpose. DfE should ensure funding is available for schools to access high-quality continued professional development for oracy which can be used to share training and resources across schools, and extend the remit of English hubs beyond Year 1 with oracy as a key support area.</p>
<p>ng, M. (2015). Influence of socioeconomic disadvantages on mathematics achievement: A multilevel cohort analysis. <i>The Journal of Educational Research</i>, 108(5), 347–357. https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2014.899956</p>	<p>Multilevel Cohort Analysis Longitudinal study of students from Grades 3 – 10 to examine impact of SES on performance based on multi-level modelling.</p>	<p>n/a</p>	<p>Focused on student- and school-level factors associated with performance in numeracy, as well as students prior (grade 3) attainment.</p>	<p>Students in a third-grade cohort in Hawaii ($n=9,953$), who were enrolled in 186 elementary were tracked from Grade 3 (2002) to Grade 10 (2009).</p>	<p>This study analyzed the most salient predictors at the student and school levels to identify their long-term impact on mathematics achievement from the elementary grades to high school. The findings suggest that of all the individual factors Grade 3 mathematics achievement was the most crucial predictor for future mathematics achievement. Economic disadvantage at the student and school level has a negative impact on achievement. Furthermore, individual characteristics had approximately four times the predictive power of school-level characteristics. Based on this, the authors questions whether schools should be held accountable for student-performance in mathematics. The stressed the importance of early intervention.</p>

